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1 Executive Summary

The NECCTON D6.2 report describes the additions and improvements made to the suite of marine biogeochemical models used in NECCTON, in connexion to the modelling of the benthic system and, in particular, suspended particulate matter (SPM), benthic flora, and benthic fauna habitat suitability. This deliverable documents the codes that have been developed in WP6 and are available on Github.

The current biogeochemical models, including those used in the Copernicus Marine Service, oversimplify modelling of the benthic compartment. In particular, they mostly ignore the effect of benthic life variability on benthic pelagic coupling, while SPM modelling mainly focuses on the organic component of SPM and usually oversimplifies the deposition/erosion processes.

Here, we describe new formulations and parameterizations of SPM. These additions include refined parameterisations of sinking, flocculation, deposition and resuspension. Specifically, these new formulations include the effect of waves derived from wave products provided by CMS.

Current ocean numerical models also oversimplify or completely ignore the variability of seafloor life and its impact on biogeochemical cycles and ecosystem functioning. By providing regional maps of the ecological processes delivered by the benthos (e.g. biomixing, biodeposition), we can assess how the variability of the functions of macrobenthos may constrain diagenetic models. Moreover, we have developed correlative models based on machine learning algorithms (i.e. Species Distribution Models, SDMs) to reconstruct the ecological niche and the distribution of a total of 339 benthic fauna species and 2 seagrass species (*Posidonia oceanica* and *Cymodocea nodosa*).

2 Introduction

2.1 Scope of the document

The objective of the document is to describe the additions and improvements made to the suite of marine biogeochemical models currently used in NECCTON, in connexion to the modelling of the benthic system and, in particular, suspended particulate matter (SPM), benthic flora, and fauna habitat suitability. This deliverable documents the codes that have been developed in WP6 and are available on Github.

2.2 Structure of the document

The document is structured as follows. Section 3 provides a synthetic list of the processes that have been parameterised and the products to which they relate. Sections 4 - 9 provide a description of each new process, including: i) background theoretical considerations, ii) a description of the implementation in code, and iii) the result of test simulations and associated analyses. A summary is provided at the end of the report. For reference, Table 1 provides a glossary of the different models.

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Table 1: Glossary of Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
Physical Models	
GOTM	General Ocean Turbulence Model
NEMO	Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean
HYCOM	Hybrid Coordinate Ocean Model
Coupling Frameworks	
FABM	Framework for Aquatic Biogeochemical Models
Marine Ecosystem and Biogeochemical Models	
ERSEM	European Regional Seas Ecosystem Model
BFM	Biogeochemical Flux Model
BAMHBI	Biogeochemical Model for Hypoxic and Benthic Influenced areas

3 Products summary

Table 2 lists the products and associated processes developed in NECCTON WP6 and described in this deliverable.

Table 2 List of products, processes, associated models, the URL of the associated code repository and the domain area where the models are run.

Associated product(s)	Process(es)	Model	Code repository [branch]	Application domain
Suspended particulate matter	SPM dynamics	BFM	https://github.com/giubonino/SPMmodule	Tyrrhenian Sea
Suspended particulate matter	SPM dynamics	ERSEM	https://github.com/pmlmodelling/ersem-neccton	Northwest European Shelf
Suspended particulate matter	SPM dynamics	BAMHBI	https://github.com/mchoblet/SPM_wave_resuspension	Black Sea
Benthic Flora	Benthic Floa Mapping of Posidonia oceanica.	BFM	Link to Benthic Flora	Mediterranean Sea
Benthic Flora	Benthic Flora mapping of <i>Cymodocea nodosa</i>	BFM	Link to Benthic Flora	Mediterranean Sea
Benthic Functions	Benthic functions mapping	BAMHBI		Black Sea
Benthic Fauna	Mussels modelling	BAMHBI		Black Sea

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4 Suspended Particulate Matter

4.1 Introduction

Suspended particulate matter (SPM) collectively refers to the inorganic (e.g., mineral) and organic particulates suspended in the water column. River discharges, production/destruction and transport in the water column, exchange with the sediment via the erosion/deposition processes and sediment degradation collectively govern SPM dynamics. SPM influences water column clarity and quality and from that, production levels. It can also act as a vector for the transfers of pollutants and contaminants. NECCTON has implemented support for simulating SPM by developing a new SPM module for the fine-scale, unstructured hydrodynamic model SHYFEM-MPI. Model testing in 3D used a local, high-resolution model domain for the Tyrrhenian Sea. Rewriting this module for FABM and incorporating it into the ERSEM model will support the delivery of a new SPM product for the Northwest European Shelf domain. A separate model of SPM developed for BAMHBI was run with NEMO to study the transport of organic SPM in the Black Sea.

In this section, we describe the processes governing SPM dynamics and their implementation in the three different models. The SPM SHYFEM-MPI and BAMHBI SPM models were tested in 3D. The FABM implementation, a part of the SPM SHYFEM-MPI model, was tested using a combination of PyFABM and 1-D simulations, where the PyFABM tool enables studying model behaviour in a 0D setting.

4.2 Suspended Particulate Matter Dynamics

4.2.1 Background

Even after putting aside suspended particles of biological origin, marine sediments are extremely diverse and occur in a wide range of different sizes and shapes, and with varying composition. Many studies categorise particles according to their physical size – a property that strongly influences particle transport dynamics.

Type	Clast name	Size range
Coarse grained (gravel) Non-cohesive	Boulder	> 256 mm
	Cobble	64 mm – 256 mm
	Pebble	4 mm – 64 mm
	Granule	2 mm – 4 mm
Medium grained (sand) Non-cohesive	Coarse	500 μ m – 2 mm
	Medium	250 μ m – 500 μ m
	Fine	63 μ m – 250 μ m
Fine grained (mud) Cohesive	Silt	2 μ m – 63 μ m
	Clay	< 2 μ m

Table 3 Grain classification based on grain size (Wentworth, 1922).

Table 3 summarises the major inorganic sediment classes, grouped according to their grain size. Particles measuring > 2 mm in size, classified as gravel, includes small granules and pebbles as well as large cobbles and boulders. The large size of gravels results in movement from location to location largely through rolling, sliding, and hopping along the bed (saltation) with transport in suspension only

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rarely. Sand particles vary in size from 63 μm up to 2 mm and move readily in suspension – especially the smaller size fractions. Sand particles are considered non-cohesive, meaning that individual grains behave independently of other sand grains. This contrasts with marine muds, which includes silt and clay particles smaller than 63 μm in size. In suspension, electrostatic forces aggregate mud particles at a sufficiently high concentrations to form larger flocs that differ markedly in transport properties to the constituent particles from which they formed. On the seabed, these same cohesive forces can impede erosion and increase bed resistance to scour. In mixed beds, and in the water column, the presence of mud can impede the transport dynamics of sand grains. However, current understanding of these interactions and the important role of biological material is less developed than for pure mixtures.

4.2.2 Theory

Figure 1 summarises the key processes involved in the transport of both non-cohesive and cohesive sediments. The SPM model includes three fundamental processes: vertical sinking, deposition, and erosion (Figure 1). These processes are modelled differently for cohesive and non-cohesive sediment.

Figure 1: Processes affecting the dynamics of SPM

Sinking of non-cohesive particles

Non-cohesive particles sink at a rate w_s . The sinking rate can either be estimated for a given class of particles based on results of empirical studies, or it can be calculated as a function of environmental conditions and particle properties using mechanistic formulae. Calculation of the sinking rate requires specifying particle density and size. We follow the method of Soulsby (Soulsby, 1997), to derive the sinking rate of particles. The sinking rate is given by the equation:

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$$w_s = \frac{v}{d} \left((10.36^2 + 1.049D_*^3)^{\frac{1}{2}} - 10.36 \right) \quad (1)$$

where v is the kinematic viscosity of sea water ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$), d is the grain diameter (m), and D_* is the dimensionless grain diameter (see equation 8 below). v is given by the equation:

$$v = \frac{\mu}{\rho_o} \quad (2)$$

Table 4 Summary of model test configurations for SPM.

Model	Inorganic or Organic?	Wave coupling?	Test configuration	Test location
SPM	Inorganic	No	SPM with SHYFEM-MPI	Tyrrhenian Sea (3D)
BHAMBI	Organic	Yes	BHAMBI with NEMO	Black Sea (3D)
ERSEM	Inorganic	No	ERSEM with GOTM	Station L4 (1D)

where μ is the dynamic viscosity (Pa s) and ρ_o is the density of sea water (kg m^{-3}). ρ_o is taken directly from the hydrodynamic model, whereas μ is calculated from temperature and salinity (Sharqawy et al., 2010).

The dimensionless grain diameter D_* is calculated using the expression:

$$D_* = \left(\frac{g(1-s)}{v^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} d \quad (3)$$

where g is acceleration due to gravity ($= 9.81 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$); s is the ratio of the densities of grains (ρ_s) and water; and d is the grain diameter. The expression for the sinking velocity of non-cohesive sand grains has been verified through 115 measurements of sinking velocities of natural sands and irregular shaped light weight grains (Soulsby, 1997). Using this expression, 90 % of the predictions lie within 20 % of the measured value.

Sinking of cohesive particles

The behaviour of suspended mud is more complex than that of sand, with sinking rates dependent on local concentrations. In saline waters, when the dry mass concentration of cohesive particles C_{M_c} exceeds approximately 0.01 kg m^{-3} , mud particles begin to flocculate. Floccs form when grains collide and tick together, which can happen through differential settling and turbulent shear. The size of the floccs increases with the mass concentration, which increases the likelihood of collisions. The size and sinking velocity of the flocc can be much larger than that of its constituent grains; and it is important to consider flocculation effects on particle sinking rates, especially for sediment concentrations higher than 0.01 kg m^{-3} .

The approach for computing the sinking velocity of floccs depends on the total concentration of cohesive sediments in the water column. Below the concentration limit C_{fLim1} , the model does not

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consider hindered settling, and calculation of the sinking velocity of cohesive particles w_{fs} follows the simplified expression:

$$w_{fs} = kC_{M_c}^m \quad (4)$$

where k and m are empirically derived parameters. For $C_{flim1} < C_{M_c}^m \leq C_{flim2}$, we follow the approach of Whitehouse (Whitehouse et al., 2000), and compute the median settling velocity of flocs as a function of the concentration of suspended mud using the equation:

$$w_{fs} = \frac{v}{d_{fe}} \left((10.36^2 + 1.049(1 - C_f)^{4.7} D_{f*}^3)^{\frac{1}{2}} - 10.36 \right) \quad (5)$$

where d_{fe} is the effective floc diameter, C_f is the volume concentration of flocs in sea water, and D_{f*} is the dimensionless floc diameter. d_{fe} is taken to be a function of the volume concentration of the suspension, C , and is given by the expression:

$$d_{fe} = lC^{\frac{m}{2}} \quad (6)$$

where l is a length scale and m is a power coefficient identical to that used in Equation (9). The length-scale, l , is given by the relationship:

$$l = \left(\frac{19.8\rho_w v \rho_s^m k}{g(\rho_{fe} - \rho_o)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (7)$$

where ρ_{fe} is the effective density of the floc, ρ_s is the mineral density of grains (the same symbol is used for sand), and k is a second coefficient which must be empirically determined. ρ_{fe} is given by the expression:

$$\rho_{fe} = \rho_w + C_{in}(\rho_s - \rho_o) \quad (8)$$

where C_{in} is the internal volume concentration of grains inside a floc and is a parameter which must be set by the user. Its value is observed to vary in the range 0.025 – 0.04.

Returning to Equation (), the volume concentration of flocs in water, C_f , is given by the equation:

$$C_f = \frac{(\rho_s - \rho_o)C}{(\rho_e - \rho_o)} \quad (9)$$

and the dimensionless floc diameter is given by the equation:

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$$D_{f*} = \left(\frac{g(\rho_e - \rho_o)}{\rho_o v^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} d_{fe} \quad (10)$$

For $C_{flim2} < C_{M_c}^m \leq C_{flim3}$, we use a simpler formulation proposed (Van Rijn, 1993):

$$w_{fs} = 0.00462(1 - 0.01C_{M_c}^m)^{3.54} \quad (11)$$

For $C_{M_c}^m > C_{flim3}$, $w_{fs} = 1 \times 10^{-5}$.

Calculation of bottom stress

Modelling sediment dynamics near to the bed, including the processes of deposition and erosion, requires calculating bottom stress or providing it from the hydrodynamic model. Combined wave-current flows requires combining the impact of both. The bottom stress from currents is calculated with the quadratic friction law:

$$\tau_c = \rho_o c_d U^2 \quad (12)$$

where U is the absolute velocity, and c_d is the drag coefficient. Assuming a logarithmic current profile, the drag coefficient can be computed as a spatially varying value based on the thickness of the lowest water layer Δz_{bottom} and the roughness length z_0 (dependent on median grain size):

$$c_d = \kappa^{-2} \left[1 + \ln \left(\frac{z_0}{\Delta z_{\text{bottom}}} \right) \right]^{-2} \quad (13)$$

where $\kappa = 0.41$ is the von Kármán constant. Alternatively, c_d can be set to a constant value, such as 10^{-3} in the NEMO model (nonlinear bottom drag option). Although the spatially varying formulation enables a more accurate representation of sediment composition, a constant value ensures consistency between physical and biogeochemical model components.

The bottom stress from waves is computed as:

$$\tau_w = \frac{1}{2} \rho_o f_w U_w^2 \quad (14)$$

where f_w is the wave friction coefficient and U_w is the maximum horizontal orbital wave velocity. Following Soulsby (Soulsby, R. L. "Dynamics of Marine Sands." (1997).), U_w can be computed from wave model variables (significant wave height H , mean wave period T , and wave number k):

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$$U_w = \frac{\pi H}{T \sinh(kh)}$$

(15)

where h is the water depth. The wave friction coefficient f_w depends on the Reynolds number R_w and flow regime. It is computed as:

$$f_w = \max(f_{wr}, f_{ws})$$

(16)

where f_{wr} is the rough bed friction:

$$f_{wr} = 0.237 \left(\frac{A}{k_s} \right)^{-0.52}$$

(17)

with orbital amplitude $A = \frac{U_w T}{2\pi}$ and bed roughness $k_s = 2.5d_{50}$ (d_{50} being the median grain size). The smooth bed friction f_{ws} is:

$$f_{ws} = B R_w^{-N}$$

(18)

where for laminar flow ($R_w < 5 \times 10^5$), $B = 2$, $N = 0.5$; and for turbulent flow ($R_w \geq 5 \times 10^5$), $B = 0.0521$, $N = 0.187$.

The total bottom stress is computed as the vector sum of current and wave bottom shear stress, accounting for their angular difference. Wave-current interaction creates a non-linear enhancement of the bottom stress, which is calculated using empirical formulas. We use the formulation by Soulsby (1997). The mean current stress including wave enhancement is:

$$\tau_{\text{mean}} = \tau_c \left[1 + 1.2 \left(\frac{\tau_w}{\tau_w + \tau_c} \right)^{3.2} \right]$$

(19)

The total bottom shear stress incorporating the angular difference Φ between wave and current directions is computed as a vector sum:

$$\tau = \sqrt{(\tau_{\text{mean}} + \tau_w \cos(\Phi))^2 + (\tau_w \sin(\Phi))^2}$$

(20)

The angular difference Φ , requires a coordinate system conversion because wave and current directions use different conventions. Wave angles in common wave data (including CMS products) follow the ECMWF convention where 0° indicates waves coming from the north and 90° from the east.

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Current angles in ocean circulation models use 0° for currents coming from the west (in u-direction). Current direction is computed as $\arctan 2 (v, u)$ with values between $-\pi$ and π . Wave angles are transformed to the current reference system by subtracting 90° , converting from the range $0-360^\circ$ to $(-180^\circ, 180^\circ)$, inverting from clockwise to counterclockwise rotation, and converting to radians.

The minimum angular difference between wave and current directions can thus be computed as:

$$\Phi = |(\phi_w - \phi_c + \pi) \bmod 2\pi - \pi| \quad (21)$$

Deposition

Deposition refers to the settling out of sediment and its deposition on the bed. In still water, the rate of deposition of sediment from suspension dm/dt can be modelled using the near-bed concentration of suspended sediment C_b and the median settling velocity of particles w_s :

$$\frac{dm}{dt} = -C_b w_s$$

(22)

In the presence of flowing water or waves, near-bed turbulence can hinder deposition, especially for fine particles. This effect can be accounted for by defining a critical bed shear stress for deposition τ_d , which is the bed stress above which deposition does not occur. In the presence of flowing water, this effect can be modelled using the expression:

$$\frac{dm}{dt} = \begin{cases} -(1 - \tau_0/\tau_d)C_b w_s & \text{for } \tau_0 < \tau_d \\ 0 & \text{for } \tau_0 \geq \tau_d \end{cases}$$

(23)

where τ_0 is the bed-shear stress in the presence of flowing water. In the presence of flowing water and waves, τ_0 must be replaced by a term that accounts for their combined impact on bed shear stress. τ_d is a parameter that must be determined empirically for different grain types. The models give the user a choice of whether to define and use τ_d , or simply model deposition using Equation (27).

Erosion

Erosion is the process by which currents and wave action erode sediment deposited on the bed. A threshold bed shear-stress for erosion τ_e defines the bed-shear stress above which erosion occurs. In the real world, shear-stress is a function of grain type and the bed composition. Several approaches for calculating the bed shear stress from the properties of grains have been proposed for sand. The threshold bed shear-stress for a given grain type can also be derived from laboratory experiments and used as a parameter in models. Here we describe two popular models, which have been implemented within NECCTON: The Soulsby Method (Soulsby and Whitehouse, 1997), and The van Rijn Method (Rijn and C, 1984). In addition, we included an option to specify the threshold bed-shear stress for erosion as a parameter. For beds containing a mixture of sand and mud, we included a further modification of the bed shear-stress to reflect the impact of sediment cohesion on bed erosion.

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4.2.2.1.1 The Soulsby Method

The Soulsby Method calculates the critical bed shear-stress for sand grains using the equation:

$$\tau_e = gd(\rho_s - \rho_w)\theta_{cr} \quad (24)$$

where g , d , ρ_s , and ρ_w are the same as defined for sinking; and θ_{cr} is the threshold Shields parameter. Based on fits to data, Soulsby and Whitehouse (1997), derived the following expression for θ_{cr} :

$$\theta_{cr} = \frac{0.3}{1 + 1.2D_*} + 0.055(1 - e^{-0.02D_*}) \quad (25)$$

4.2.2.1.2 The van Rijn Method

The van Rijn method differs only in the approach for calculating θ_{cr} as a function of D_* :

$$\theta_{cr} = \begin{cases} 2.4 \times 10^{-1} D_*^{-0.90} & \text{for } D_* \leq 4 \\ 1.4 \times 10^{-1} D_*^{-0.64} & \text{for } 4 < D_* \leq 10 \\ 4.0 \times 10^{-2} D_*^{-0.10} & \text{for } 10 < D_* \leq 20 \\ 1.3 \times 10^{-2} D_*^{-0.29} & \text{for } 20 < D_* \leq 150 \\ 5.6 \times 10^{-2} & \text{for } D_* > 150 \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

4.2.2.1.3 Mud-sand mixtures

The Soulsby and van Rijn methods for calculating the threshold Shields parameter are specific to sandy beds. Muddy beds tend to be harder to erode because of the cohesive forces between particles. For mixed beds with a mud content greater than approximately 15 %, cohesive effects start to become important. To account for this effect, we follow the approach of van Rijn by including a dependency on mud content p_c of the bed (Van Rijn, 2007, 1993). Defining the percentage mud content as:

$$p_c = \frac{m_c}{m_t} \quad (27)$$

where m_c is the mass of cohesive sediment within the bed, and m_t is the total mass of sediment in the bed. The threshold bed shear-stress for erosion and including cohesive effects $\tau_{e,c}$ is then calculated using the equation:

$$\tau_{e,c} = \tau_e(1 + p_c)^\beta \quad (28)$$

Early work assigned the parameter β a value in the range 1.5 – 3. Later studies observed variation with the percentage of clay and fines in the bed, and the dry bulk density (van Rijn et al., 2025). However, for simplicity, we maintain the original formulation, in which β is assigned a fixed value.

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Table 5 Common SPM parameters, their units, and reference values.

Parameter	Description	Units	Reference value
ϵ	Bed porosity	-	0.4
β	Beta exponent for erosion	-	2
K	Constant used in Equation ()	-	1×10^{-3}
m	Constant used in Equation ()	-	1
C_{in}	Internal volume concentration of grains inside a floc	-	3×10^{-2}
C_{fLim1}	Mass concentration limit 1 for flocculation and settling calculation	kg m^{-3}	2
C_{fLim2}	Mass concentration limit 2 for flocculation and settling calculation	kg m^{-3}	50
C_{fLim3}	Mass concentration limit 3 for flocculation and settling calculation	kg m^{-3}	82
m_1	Parameter governing the mass per unit area eroded	kg m^{-2}	5×10^{-3}
m_2	Parameter controlling the rate of erosion at low bed concentrations	-	1×10^{-5}

4.2.2.1.4 Erosion flux

The actual erosion flux is calculated using the formulation of Ariathurai and Arulanandan (, 1978), which is also described in Warner et al. (2008).

$$\frac{dm}{dt} = m_e \left(\frac{\tau_0}{\tau_{e,c}} - 1 \right) (1 - \epsilon) \quad (29)$$

where ϵ is the bed's porosity, and m_e is an erosion coefficient given by the function:

$$m_e = \min (m_1, m_2 m) \quad (30)$$

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Here, m_1 is the bed erosion content, which can vary by orders of magnitude between locations. m_2 is a second constant which introduces a first order dependence on the amount of material in the bed at low concentrations.

4.2.3 Implementation

Support for SPM modelling has been added to three separate models: the SHYFEM-MPI hydrodynamic model, BAMHBI and ERSEM. The ERSEM SPM code is a port of the SPM SHYFEM-MPI code, which involved rewriting the module to utilise the FABM library. Table 6 lists common parameters for the models and Table 62 provides links to the code.

SPM in the Tyrrhenian sea

The new SHYFEM-MPI model of SPM dynamics includes all the processes described in Figure 1. For non-cohesive sediments, these processes include sinking, deposition, and resuspension. For cohesive sediments, we also include a parameterisation of flocculation in the water column and the sinking of flocs. A relatively simple model of the bed, developed in WP6, is also included and treated as a single layer, which may contain a varying mixture of sand and mud. The model does not attempt to represent multiple layers with varying physical properties, sediment consolidation within the bed, time varying bathymetry, or bed load transport. We deemed implementing support for modelling these processes to be outside the scope of the current project.

The SPM model has been integrated as a FORTRAN module into SHYFEM-MPI (Micaletto et al., 2022), the MPI implementation of the three-dimensional finite element hydrodynamic model SHYFEM. To solve the equations presented above, the SHYFEM-MPI model provides the SPM module with temperature and salinity fields as well as bottom stress. Parameters are specified in a single parameter file.

SPM in the North Sea

The model of SPM that was created and tested with the SHYFEM-MPI model was reimplemented in the ERSEM codebase. The model was rewritten using FABM coding conventions (see NECCTON D3.1). The implementation includes new types for non-cohesive and cohesive particles. These types enable model runs with any number of non-cohesive and cohesive particle classes. A small number of ancillary modules provide supporting functionality. Using SPM in an ERSEM model run requires specifying one or more SPM tracers in the file ERSEM *fabm.yaml*. An example ERSEM *fabm.yaml* file can be found in the git repository: <https://github.com/pmlmodelling/ersem-spm-setup>.

SPM in the Black Sea

In contrast, the BHAMBI SPM model focusses on the organic component of SPM. Many of the processes controlling the movement of organic SPM duplicate those controlling the movement of inorganic SPM. The BAMHBI model considers the additional impact of waves on the bottom shear stress (see Table 5).

The BAMHBI Black Sea implementation of sediment resuspension resulting from currents and waves is based on the NEMO-BAMHBI setup (CMS Dataset: CMS BLKSEA_ANALYSISFORECAST_BGC_007_010).

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4.2.4 Testing

In this section we describe the results of test simulations performed using the three SPM models.

SPM in the Tyrrhenian sea

Figure 2: SHYFEM-MPI domain in the Tyrrhenian Sea. Model domain and bathymetry are shown on the left and SeaBed EMODnet type in Civitavecchia domain (black line) on the right.

The numerical model has been implemented and validated for the Tyrrhenian Sea coastal region adjacent to Civitavecchia, Italy (Figure 2, 42.15°N, 11.75°E). We selected this geographical domain because of its heterogeneous bathymetric characteristics, pronounced sedimentological gradients, and diverse benthic habitat distribution, making it well suited for evaluating suspended sediment transport dynamics.

The domain extends 65 km along the coastline and 20 km offshore, encompassing both the littoral zone and the continental shelf. The bathymetric profile exhibits significant variability, ranging from shallow coastal environments to shelf depths of approximately 220 m, thereby incorporating multiple hydrodynamic regimes relevant to sediment transport processes. We varied the horizontal mesh resolution spatially, with maximum refinement ($\Delta x \approx 100$ m) in the coastal zone where bathymetric gradients and sediment dynamics require enhanced spatial resolution. The mesh gradually coarsens to approximately 1.5 km in offshore regions characterized by less pronounced spatial gradients. We achieved vertical discretization through 43 z-levels with thickness varying from 1 m at the surface to larger intervals at depth, ensuring adequate resolution of both the surface mixed layer and bottom boundary layer processes critical for sediment transport.

We performed a two-year simulation (2020-2021) after a three-year spin-up period to achieve dynamical equilibrium in the physical components. The simulation was forced by hourly surface atmospheric variables from the ERA5 reanalysis (Hersbach et al., 2020). We conducted the hydrodynamic initialization using three-dimensional fields of temperature, salinity, and currents from the CMS Mediterranean Sea Physical Reanalysis system (Escudier et al., 2020). For the benthic and

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Figure 3: Model domain showing the unstructured mesh and monitoring stations used for model validation, including a scale bar and north arrow for reference. Right: Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) analysis for Sea Surface Temperature (SST, top panel) and Suspended Particulate Matter (SPM, bottom panel) at each monitoring station for the period 2020-2021. RMSE values are calculated comparing model outputs with ESA SST CCI observations for SST and CMS Global Sea Level-3 SPM product for SPM concentrations.

pelagic SPM, we used the Seabed Habitats dataset (Figure 2, <https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en/seabed-habitats>), to identify sediment classes and create initial spatial distribution of each sediment class. We identified three distinct granulometric classes: the first class comprises cohesive mud particles with a characteristic diameter of 40 μm , incorporating flocculation processes. The second class represents non-cohesive fine sand with an 80 μm diameter, governed by individual particle dynamics. A third class with 0.1 m diameter was implemented to represent rocky substrates, functioning as a passive benthic boundary without participating in erosion-deposition cycles.

The spatial heterogeneity of benthic sediment distributions was reconstructed as follows (Figure 2): we characterized fine mud environments by an 80:20 ratio of mud to fine sand, whereas we initialized sandy substrates with the inverse proportion. Mixed sedimentary facies, including muddy sand and sandy mud classifications, were configured with equal proportions of both constituents. The initial sediment distribution was parameterized with a uniform mass density of 660 kg m^{-2} across the seabed, corresponding to a 0.25 m thickness assuming a characteristic sediment density of 2650 kg m^{-3} . Each grid point has a total of 660 kg m^{-2} of sediment divided among the sediment classes. We defined the initial condition of each sediment class upon the previous seabed type partition table; for example, a grid point in "Fine mud" type contained 480 kg m^{-2} in the mud class and 120 kg m^{-2} in the sand class. Initial suspended particulate matter concentrations in the water column (i.e., pelagic system) were set to zero to allow realistic spatial distributions to develop through physical transport mechanisms. Lateral open boundary conditions for the suspended sediments were prescribed from CMS MED Reanalysis data (Escudier et al., 2020) for the physics and from CMS GlobalSea Level-3 SPM product based on the Copernicus-GlobColour product (CMS product OCEANCOLOUR_GLO_BGC_L3_MY_009_103) for the sediment classes. As a first simplistic approach, we split satellite SPM data equally between the two classes and distributed them downward homogeneously.

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Model performance evaluation was conducted through quantitative comparison of simulated and observed SST and SPM (i.e., sum of the mud and sand concentrations) at multiple reference stations distributed throughout the domain (Figure 3). The SPM model was validated using the CMS Global Sea Level-3 SPM product, whereas the hydrodynamic model skill was assessed using Level 4 sea surface temperature data, available via the Copernicus Climate Data Store, which provides high-resolution (0.05°) daily satellite observations (Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S), 2019).

Figure 4: Time series comparison of modeled (blue line) and observed (black dots) total SPM concentrations (MUD + SAND) at four representative stations during 2020-2021. (a) Station 3-CTD showing coastal dynamics (RMSE=1.74 g m⁻³, n=516); (b) Station SPM-N demonstrating offshore behaviour (RMSE=0.66 g m⁻³, n=512); (c) Station IT_m1vt04_12 representing transitional waters (RMSE=0.75 g m⁻³, n=521); and (d) Station SPM-S capturing southern domain characteristics (RMSE=0.90 g m⁻³, n=519). RMSE values and number of observations (n) are reported for each station.

The RMSE analysis (Figure 3) revealed consistent model performance across all monitoring stations. For SST, we observed RMSE values ranging between 0.6°C and 1.0°C, with the best performance at coastal stations (e.g., SPM-S with RMSE = 0.62°C) and slightly higher values at offshore locations (e.g., CTD-3 with RMSE = 1.05°C). These values fall within the expected range for regional coastal models and indicate robust hydrodynamic performance.

SPM simulations showed varying degrees of accuracy across the domain, with RMSE values ranging from (0.66 - 2.2) g m⁻³. The lowest RMSE values were found at stations SPM-S (0.65 g m⁻³) and SPM-C (0.75 g m⁻³), indicating particularly good model performance in reproducing suspended sediment dynamics in these locations. Higher RMSE values at stations closer to the coast (e.g., CTD-2 and CTD-3 with RMSE > 1.7 g m⁻³) reflect the increased complexity of sediment dynamics in nearshore environments, where interactions between waves, currents, and bathymetry lead to more variable SPM concentrations.

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Figure 5: Model results from NEMO-BHAMBI, using a configuration for the Black Sea showing the mean bottom stress on the North Western Black Sea Shelf (left); the contribution of waves to the total bottom stress (centre); and the frequency of resuspension events throughout the year (right).

Time series analysis at selected stations (Figure 4) provides additional insights into model performance. At station 3-CTD, despite an RMSE of 1.74 g m^{-3} , the model successfully captured the temporal evolution of SPM peaks, particularly during high-concentration events ($>4 \text{ g m}^{-3}$). The SPM-N station showed excellent agreement between modelled and observed concentrations (RMSE = 0.66 g m^{-3}), with the model accurately reproducing both the timing and magnitude of concentration variations. At station IT_m1vt04_12, we observed a good correlation between simulated and observed patterns, with an RMSE of 0.75 g m^{-3} , although the model slightly underestimated some peak concentrations. The SPM-S station time series (RMSE = 0.90 g m^{-3}) demonstrates the model's capability to capture seasonal variations in SPM concentrations, particularly in the winter months when increased wave activity enhances sediment resuspension.

The number of observations for each station ($n \approx 515\text{-}521$) provided a robust statistical basis for the validation. From these comprehensive analyses, we can conclude that the SPM model demonstrates good skill in reproducing SPM variability in the Civitavecchia coastal area, with particularly strong performance in capturing temporal patterns and seasonal variations. The slightly higher RMSE values near the coast align with the inherent complexity of coastal sediment dynamics and the challenges in representing highly variable nearshore processes.

SPM in the Black Sea

Preliminary experiments at $1/6^\circ$ resolution over the period 1990-2023 revealed that wave coupling significantly affects bottom stress in the shallowest areas of the Black Sea Northwestern shelf, where most sediment resuspension occurs (Figure 5), particularly during fall and winter. This setup used a static threshold of 0.02 Pa for resuspension because we have not yet implemented the SHYFEM based variable critical bottom stress module in NEMO-BAMHBI. Until now, the setup focused only on the resuspension of particulate organic matter. The inclusion of resuspension-driven suspended matter dynamics in NEMO-BAMHBI led to significant differences in the biogeochemical model when we included waves. Comparison of three simulation types (with wave and current resuspension, with current-only resuspension, and without resuspension) revealed that current-only and no-resuspension simulations produced similar results, because bottom currents alone were insufficient to trigger resuspension. Wave-induced resuspension increased the average POM concentration in the shelf water column by approximately 30 %. Through remineralization of this organic material, wave-induced resuspension also led to a comparable increase in shelf nutrient concentrations.

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The high inertia of sediments in NEMO-BAMHBI, which can extend up to 10 years, add a technical consideration that necessitates adequately long model spin-up times when modifying parameters that affect sediment dynamics.

Figure 6: Hovmoller plots of SPM concentrations at Station L4 in the Western English Channel, which were simulated using a 1D configuration of GOTM-ERSEM. The figure shows the modelled concentration of sand (a) and mud (b).

SPM in the North Sea

The ERSEM-SPM model was tested using a combination of PyFABM and the 1D model GOTM. Notebooks showing the model exactly reproduces published check values for sinking rates are provided in the repository: <https://github.com/pmlmodelling/ersem-spm-setup>. In 1D, we produced a simple test run using a GOTM configuration for Station L4 in the Western English Channel (also available in the ersem-spm-setup GitHub repository). Sample output is shown in Figure 6 for a run with two sediment classes: sand particles with a diameter of 80 microns and mud particles with a diameter of 10 microns. The model was initialized with an equal mix of mud and sand in the bed, and a total bed sediment concentration of 2000 kg m⁻². The water column was initialised with a concentration of 1 kg m⁻³ of both sand and mud, which was homogeneous throughout the water column, and we used a high, fixed bed stress of 2 Pa. This value exceeded the threshold for erosion of both sand and mud particles, given an initial equal mixture within the bed. Over time, both mud and sand erode from the bed. We did not impose a threshold bed shear stress for deposition, which allows deposition of both sand and mud particles. Given the faster sinking rate of the larger sand grains, sand grains settle back on the bed at a faster rate, and the concentration of mud in the water column quickly exceeds that of sand. As more mud erodes from the bed, the bed becomes less cohesive, and erosion rates increase. When more vigorous turbulent mixing occurs in the water column, as is the case on

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12th January, both mud and sand grains mix further up the water column. These results align with the mathematical model of SPM dynamics described here.

SPM in the Black Sea

The NECCON WP6 (and WP5) SPM products for the Black Sea will also include an explicit representation of mineral SPM (such as sand, mud, and clay). We plan to add two mineral SPM tracers to the existing NEMO-BAMHBI Black Sea configuration (Gregoire et al., 2025) to represent fine and coarse mineral SPM with low and high sinking speeds, respectively. This design builds on work by Stanev and Kandilarov (2012; 10.1007/s10236-012-0520-1), who successfully simulated the purely physical advection and diffusion of such tracers for the Black Sea without a biogeochemical model, achieving reasonable agreement with satellite data.

In addition to advection and diffusion, the mineral SPM tracers will settle on the sea floor and resuspend in shallow regions where currents and waves exert sufficient stress on the bottom, particularly during the stormy winter season (as described for organic SPM in the previous section).

The mineral SPM tracers interact with the biogeochemical model by enhancing light attenuation via an SPM-specific term in the attenuation formulation, potentially improving the model's light representation. The mineral SPM tracers thus function as relatively passive biogeochemical tracers; for now, we plan no direct interaction (e.g., via aggregation) with other biogeochemical tracers such as particulate organic carbon.

Forcings and initialization: For the riverine SPM load (in terms of concentration), we are using three data sources. For the Danube, the major river discharging into the Black Sea, Total Suspended Matter (assumed to be mineral SPM) the TransNational Monitoring Network of the Danube River Basin (TNMN) publishes a monthly timeseries. For all other rivers, we use estimates from the GEMS-GLORI world river discharge database doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.804574, and SPM estimates near river mouths from the Copernicus-GlobColour Bio-Geo-Chemical L3 product. Besides the Danube as a sediment source, we felt it particularly important to include the Caucasian rivers which carry significant sediment load (Jipa and Panin 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2018.08.006>). We will multiply the discharge by the river runoff (data and methodology behind runoff dataset to be published alongside the next Black Sea Biogeochemistry Analysis and Forecast [10.25423/CMCC/BLKSEA_ANALYSISFORECAST_BGC_007_010](https://doi.org/10.25423/CMCC/BLKSEA_ANALYSISFORECAST_BGC_007_010)). We will initialize water column surface SPM concentrations from the Copernicus-GlobColour Bio-Geo-Chemical L3 product, and derive initial seabed mineral SPM concentrations either from a multi-year model spin-up from zero or from the EMODnet EUSeaMap 2023 product (<https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en/seabed-habitats>), which provides only a coarse categorization of seabed substrates but can help constrain the regions of fine and coarse substrate.

Modification of Light Attenuation scheme: The primary light attenuation scheme used in NEMO-BAMHBI divides light into three wavebands (short, long, infrared) and uses absorption and backscattering properties (inherent optical properties) of different seawater constituents in those wavebands (Grégoire et al., 2025) Given the high number of parameters involved, introducing additional SPM-specific parameters would reduce the traceability of the light attenuation model's behavior.

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We thus rely on a simplified light attenuation calculation based solely on apparent optical properties of the seawater constituents (k_{CHL} , k_{POC} , k_{SPM}) and pure water itself (k_{water}):

$$KD_{\text{PAR}} = k_{\text{water}} + k_{\text{CHL}} * \text{CHL} + k_{\text{POC}} * \text{POC} + k_{\text{SPM}} * \text{SPM},$$

using literature values for these parameters. While we performed initial tests with BGC-ARGO data from the Black Sea were to estimate a locally calibrated regression equation for the Black Sea, this approach has not been pursued for now because BGC-ARGO does not directly measure POC and mineral SPM.

Initial experiments with a single SPM class instead of two aim to strike a balance between river inflow, resuspension and deposition, and export into the deep sea, where we consider the deep ocean an infinite sink. The key question is whether the resulting balance represents satellite SPM products reasonably well, after which we can add the layer of complexity of two SPM classes. Simplified light attenuation models are standard in most operational biogeochemical ocean models (e.g., PISCES (<https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-8-2465-2015>), ERSEM (<https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-9-1293-2016>), BFM (<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jmarsys.2006.03.006>), ERGOM (<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jmarsys.2015.08.001>), FESOM-RECOM (<https://elib.suub.uni-bremen.de/diss/docs/00011278.pdf>)). While recent advances (e.g., Macé 2025 <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2024-3682>) have incorporated spectral radiative transfer modeling for the Black Sea, we opt for a simplified light attenuation scheme because of computational constraints.

Validation Plans: Model validation will rely on satellite-derived non-algal SPM products generated using standard (non-regionally tuned) algorithms. The primary dataset will be the Global Ocean Colours, Copernicus-GlobColour, Bio-Geo-Chemical L3 product (daily) from satellite observations (1997-ongoing), providing daily data at 4 km resolution (https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/OCEANCOLOUR_GLO_BGC_L3_MY_009_103/description). Additionally, we will use KD490 attenuation data from the same product to compare light attenuation with and without SPM inclusion.

Future Analysis: Future validation work can incorporate refined SPM retrieval algorithms. Subirade et al. (2024) compare different algorithms on a global scale (<https://doi.org/10.1364/OE.529712>), while Constantin et al. (2024) offer Black Sea-specific improvements to reflectance based SPM algorithms (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2024.108871>). BGC-ARGO data may also be useful for estimating SPM from backscattering measurements, though we must limit this approach to the central basin given the absence of float coverage in coastal and shelf regions, where SPM concentrations peak.

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5 Habitat Suitability models

5.1 Mediterranean Sea

5.1.1 Introduction

We used correlative models based on machine learning algorithms (i.e. Species Distribution Models, SDMs) to reconstruct the ecological niche of the considered species. We performed all calculations in the R computing environment (v4.2.2). We effectively modeled the distribution a total of 339 benthic fauna species and 2 seagrass species (*Posidonia oceanica* and *Cymodocea nodosa*). The models for benthic fauna and seagrass do not differ in terms of algorithms fitted, but they differ in the implementation because of differences in a priori knowledge on the ecology of species. This constraint resulted in the use of a smaller number of predictors to fit the benthic fauna models.

5.1.2 Material and Methods

5.1.2.1. Species occurrences

For benthic species, we retrieved occurrence data from three distinct data sources: (i) the Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS), (ii) the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), and (iii) the Bottom Trawl Survey for the Mediterranean (MEDITS). We downloaded the OBIS and GBIF data using the R packages ‘robis’ and ‘rgbif’, respectively. The data were queried using a polygon encircling the Mediterranean, and retained only data after 2000. We flagged and removed data with incorrect or incomplete dates or data falling on the land, because GBIF also contains occurrences based on terrestrial records. Next, we performed a taxonomic check by comparing the available list species with the taxonomy accepted by the World Register of Marine Species (WORMS) using a fuzzy match algorithm (‘worms’ package). This procedure resolves potential taxonomic ambiguities resulting from potentially different taxonomic standards used by different data providers. For seagrass, we retrieved occurrences of *P. oceanica* and *C. nodosa* from published literature (Chefaoui et al. 2017, 2018).

To match occurrence data with the spatial resolution of the physical and biogeochemical predictors used as predictors in the SDMs (see next section), we thinned the data by retaining one species record per each ~4.5x4.5-km grid cell.

We retained benthic species data present in at least $n = 120$ grid cells, a threshold we found appropriate as a minimum number of points to fit the models. We removed Cephalopoda as they have a much higher mobility than other classes. We also removed invasive species (*C. sapidus*, *P. gibbesi*) because their present range might not match the potential range. We also removed commercially exploited species (*P. longirostris*, *A. foliacea*, *A. antennatus*, *N. norvegicus*) because the patterns of species distribution might be heavily influenced by fishing activities (not modeled here). We used the resulting benthic species dataset, comprised ~125 000 occurrence records for 353 species and 20 classes, to fit the models (Figure 7). The resulting seagrass dataset consists of 543 points for *P. oceanica* and 276 points for *C. nodosa* used to fit the model (Figure 8).

5.1.2.2 Environmental predictors

We obtained most of the environmental predictors used to fit SDMs from reanalysis of the Mediterranean Sea physics (Escudier et al. 2020, 2021), biogeochemistry (Teruzzi et al. 2021; Cossarini

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et al. 2021), and sea waves (Korres et al. 2021) data provided by the Copernicus Marine Service (CMS; Le Traon et al., 2019). The physics and biogeochemistry reanalysis products have a resolution of $\sim 4.5 \times 4.5$ km and 125 unevenly spaced active vertical layers (thickness ranging between 2 and 100 m, increasing with depth). We downloaded the data with a monthly resolution for the period 2000 – 2020. The extracted physical variables included sea water velocity (V_m), potential temperature (T), and salinity concentration (SAL). The extracted biogeochemical variables included pH (pH), concentrations of ammonium (NH_4), nitrate (NO_3), phosphate (PO_4), dissolved oxygen (O_2), chlorophyll (CHL), and phytoplankton expressed as carbon (PHY). The extracted sea waves variables included wave significant height ($VHM0$) and wave mean period from variance spectral density second frequency moment ($VTM02$). For all physical and biogeochemical variables, we selected the physicochemical conditions of the vertical layer just above sea bottom. Finally, for all variables, we calculated the median, maximum, minimum, and range of their physicochemical conditions over the 240 monthly maps covering the twenty-year period. Additionally, we used the high resolution GEBCO bathymetric map (0.5 x 0.5 km; Weatherall et al., 2015) to calculate the average depth ($DEPTH$) and slope ($SLOPE$) of each 4.5 x 4.5 km grid cell. Finally, we included sediment data based on the seafloor sediment map produced by the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet, Kaskela et al., 2019). Thus, our predictors included the percentage of grid cells covered by sand ($SAND$), mud (MUD), and mixed sediment (MIX).

Figure 7: Spatial distribution of benthic fauna points used to fit the model. The color scale counts the number of points falling in each pixel. The grey shaded area represents areas where seafloor depth is shallower than 800 m. The labels represent the main mediterranean basins: alb: Alborean Sea; nwm: north-west Mediterranean; swm: south-west Mediterranean; tyr: Tyrrhenian sea; ion: Ionian sea; adr: Adriatic sea; aeg: Aegean sea; lev: Levantine sea. The top-right insert represents the depth distribution of the occurrence points. The grey shaded area is the spatial extent where we projected models.

To retain a parsimonious subset of predictors for fitting the model and avoid overfitting, we performed a hierarchical cluster analysis based on a distance matrix, using 1 minus the absolute value of Spearman's correlation coefficient ($1 - |r|$) as a measure of predictor dissimilarity. We used the threshold of $r = 0.7$ to identify 17 clusters of predictors and retained one predictor for each cluster. Finally, we assessed the multicollinearity of the retained predictors with the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF, function 'vifstep' in the package 'usdm'), resulting in a shorter list of predictors.

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We fitted Seagrass models using 12 predictors, namely: SLOPE, NO3median, DEPTH, Tmedian, pHmedian, O2median, VHM0median, PO4median, Tmin, SALmedian, CHLmedian, Vmmax. We did not include sediment coverage predictors because seagrasses are habitat-forming organisms that can alter the substrate composition.

We fitted benthic fauna models using 7 predictors, namely: O2median, CHLmedian, Tmedian, Tmin, SALmedian, Vmmedian, and SAND. We did not include waves predictors because most of the modeled benthic species are not affected by waves actions. We also did not include bathymetric predictors (DEPTH and SLOPE) because they might act as an indirect predictor (i.e. mask the effects of other predictors such as temperature, even if moderately correlated), and therefore bias model projections when extrapolating to different geographic areas (Guisan and Zimmermann 2000).

Figure 8: Geographic distribution of (a) *P. oceanica* and (b) *C. nodosa* data used to fit the models. The grey shaded area is the spatial extent where models were projected.

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Table 6: Predictors mean (25th-75th percentiles) used in the seagrass models over the studied domain, and for the points where species occurrences are available. All predictors' statistics are calculated over a period of 20 years (2000 – 2020).

Predictor name	Units	Description	Mediterranean	P. oceanica	C. nodosa
SLOPE	m m ⁻¹	Median cell slope based on GEBCO bathymetry	0.3 (0.1-0.7)	0.7 (0.4-1.1)	0.6 (0.3-1)
NO3 _{median}	mmol m ⁻³	Concentration of nitrate close to the bottom, median of monthly means	0.8 (0.4-1.7)	0.8 (0.6-1.5)	0.7 (0.5-1.2)
DEPTH	m	Median cell depth based on GEBCO bathymetry	23 (16-31)	20 (15-26)	19 (13.5-24.5)
T _{median}	°C	Sea water potential temperature close to the bottom, median of monthly means	17.3 (15.8-20.4)	16.3 (15.0-17.6)	16.8 (15.9-17.7)
pH _{median}	-	Sea water pH close to the bottom, median of monthly means	8.11 (8.08-8.13)	8.11 (8.1-8.13)	8.1 (8.09-8.12)
O2 _{median}	mmol m ⁻³	Concentration of dissolved oxygen close to the bottom, median of monthly means	237.6 (226.1-245.4)	239.1 (229.7-243.8)	241.7 (236.7-245.8)
VHM0 _{median}	m	Sea wave significant height, median of monthly means	0.6 (0.5-0.8)	0.5 (0.4-0.9)	0.5 (0.4-0.6)
PO4 _{median}	mmol m ⁻³	Concentration of orthophosphate close to the bottom, median of monthly means	0.1 (0.1-0.3)	0.2 (0.1-0.6)	0.2 (0.1-0.5)
T _{min}	°C	Sea water potential temperature close to the bottom, minimum of monthly means	13.1 (11.7-14.6)	13.1 (12.5-13.7)	12.9 (11.7-13.4)
SAL _{median}	psu	Sea water salinity close to the bottom, median of monthly means	38.2 (37.8-38.7)	38.1 (37.9-38.7)	37.8 (37.4-38.1)

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CHL _{median}	mg m ⁻³	Concentration of chlorophyll-a close to the bottom, median of monthly means	0.14 (0.1-0.25)	0.12 (0.09-0.17)	0.14 (0.1-0.22)
Vm _{max}	m s ⁻¹	Sea water velocity close to the bottom, maximum of monthly means	0.05 (0.04-0.07)	0.05 (0.03-0.07)	0.04 (0.03-0.07)

Table 7: Predictors mean (25th-75th percentiles) used in the benthic fauna models over the studied domain, and for the points where species occurrences are available. All predictor statistics were calculated over a period of 20 years (2000 – 2020).

Predictor name	Units	Description	Value
CHL _{median}	mg m ⁻³	Concentration of chlorophyll-a close to the bottom, median of monthly means	0.009 (0-0.119)
O2 _{median}	mmol m ⁻³	Concentration of dissolved oxygen close to the bottom, median of monthly means	227.9 (212.6-240.8)
SAL _{median}	psu	Sea water salinity close to the bottom, median of monthly means	38.6 (38.3-38.8)
T _{median}	°C	Sea water potential temperature close to the bottom, median of monthly means	14.4 (13.9-15.9)
T _{min}	°C	Sea water potential temperature close to the bottom, minimum of monthly means	13.5 (12.9-13.9)
Vm _{median}	m s ⁻¹	Sea water velocity close to the bottom, median of monthly means	0.008 (0.005-0.013)

5.1.2.1. Model Formulation and parameterization

We used the package ‘biomod2’ (Thuiller et al. 2009) in the R v4.3.1 computing environment (R Core Team 2022) to train Species Distribution Models (SDMs), produce ensembles, and predict habitat suitability distributions for seagrass and benthic fauna.

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5.1.2.1.1 Pseudo-absences

For each species, we used occurrence and pseudo-absence (P-Abs) data to fit the models. We combined two different sampling strategies to generate our P-Abs ($n = 10000$): ‘density-dependent’ and ‘environmentally stratified’. The first half of the P-Abs ($n = 5000$) was generated according to a density-dependent strategy because both benthic fauna and seagrass occurrences displayed a strong sampling bias towards the north-western part of the Mediterranean (Fig. 1). To correct for this bias, we inferred the P-Abs based on the kernel smoothing intensity of all occurrence points (functions ‘rSSI’ and ‘density.ppp’ in the ‘spatstat’ package, setting the smoothing bandwidth parameter to 3). This method generated a higher density of P-Abs closer to species observations, mimicking the same sampling effort distribution (Righetti et al. 2019; Descombes et al. 2022). We generated the second half of the P-Abs ($n = 5000$) based on a stratified subdivision of the environmental range. For this, we classified both the median temperature and salinity predictor rasters into three bins (splitting data at the 0.3 and 0.6 quantiles) of continuous values, regrouped them into unique categories of temperature-salinity ($n = 9$), and sampled an equal number of pseudo-absences for each combination. This method guarantees that all environmental strata were represented in the training dataset and reduces extrapolation errors at the edge of the species’ environmental niche (Descombes et al. 2022; Da Re et al. 2023). Finally, we replicated the above procedure three times for each species to account for the variability in the P-abs generation.

5.1.2.1.2 Model calibration

We fitted four types of models: a generalized linear model (GLM), a generalized additive model (GAM), a random forest (RF), and an artificial neural network (ANN). We fitted intermediate complexity models to balance the fitting capacity with the ability to extrapolate to unsampled environmental conditions, i.e., to prevent overfitting following the guidelines in Brun et al. (2020). We fitted GLMs with linear and quadratic terms; set the regularization in the GAM smooth term to 3; set a minimum size of 40 for terminal nodes and a number of 1000 trees for RF. We trained ANN models with 3 hidden layers and a decay of 0.1, which we found appropriate to avoid overfitting for the specific datasets.

Finally, we used the biomod2 default setting of equal prevalence to presences and P-abs (i.e., the sum of the presences weights equals the sum of P-abs weights). This way, the influence of P-abs in the calibration of each single model was kept constant, regardless of the number of presence points used for fitting.

5.1.2.1.3 Model evaluation and ensemble

Since there are no independent validation datasets, we used a spatial block approach (Valavi et al. 2019) to split the data (occurrences and P-abs) in training (80 %) and evaluation (20 %) datasets. Spatial clusters were defined using a k-medoid approach (‘pam’ function in the ‘cluster’ package, see Brun et al., 2020). Shortly, the method first creates spatially independent clusters of occurrence data and then aggregates the P-abs based on the nearest neighbor algorithm. The result is a spatially structured dataset where training and evaluation data occupy distinct geographic areas, and to test the model’s ability to extrapolate to distinct geographic areas.

In the model’s training phase, we employed 5-fold cross validation (80% of the data for calibration, 20% for validation), and repeated it three times, thus yielding a total amount of 180 models (5 cross validation folds X 3 repetitions X 3 PA datasets X 4 models) for each species. We used the Area under

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the Receiving Operating Curve (AUC), the True Skill Statistics (TSS, Allouche et al. 2006) to evaluate the performance metrics of each model for both the validation and calibration data sets. Additionally, we assessed model performance using Boyce's index, a presence-only metric (Hirzel et al. 2006). We used the validation AUC and TSS to assess single model performance. Additionally, we compared both validation and calibration AUC and TSS and evaluated how they differed to assess model's overfitting (Radosavljevic and Anderson 2014).

After discarding models with $AUC < 0.7$, we generated a model ensemble for each species by weight averaging each model based on its AUC score. We assessed the importance of predictors in the final ensemble using a permutation approach, and followed by randomly permuting each predictor, one at a time, and made model predictions accordingly. We then compared each prediction with and without permutation using Pearson's correlation coefficient (ρ) and determined predictor importance as $1 - |\rho|$. This process was repeated three times for each predictor, after which we considered average variable importance.

5.1.2.1.4 Model projections

We used the ensemble models to predict species' habitat suitability spatially over the study area. To binarize the habitat suitability score to suitable and unsuitable habitats, we used a threshold that balances omission and commission errors (Guisan et al. 2017). Since both *P. oceanica* and *C. nodosa* are coastal organisms strongly limited by depth (Duarte 1991), we only retained them in the projection suitable cells with bottom layer average depth < 40 m. Given that we could not define expert-based depth thresholds for each benthic species, we constrained model predictions to realistic depth ranges by assuming that the species-specific upper depth ranges could be 30% shallower than the current 5th depth percentile, and the lower range could be 30% deeper than the current 95th depth percentile. We also considered 800 m depth as a 'hard' threshold given the lack of available data for deeper sites.

5.1.3 Results and Discussion

5.1.3.1 Results for Seagrass models

The ensemble models for seagrasses yielded good performances, with an AUC of 0.80 for *P. oceanica* and 0.84 for *C. nodosa*, a TSS of 0.47 for *P. oceanica* and 0.59 for *C. nodosa*; and a Boyce index of 0.90 for *P. oceanica* and 0.92 for *C. nodosa*. The most important predictors for *P. oceanica* were median temperature (T_{median} , $1 - \rho = 0.25$), bottom slope (SLOPE, $1 - \rho = 0.20$), bottom depth (DEPTH, $1 - \rho = 0.17$), and nitrate concentration (NO_3 ; $1 - \rho = 0.13$), with an optimal species response at lower NO_3 (≤ 2.0 mmol m^{-3}) and intermediate temperature ($\leq 17^\circ\text{C}$). The most important predictors for *C. nodosa* were bottom slope (SLOPE, $1 - \rho = 0.24$), bottom oxygen (O_2 , $1 - \rho = 0.20$), nitrate concentration (NO_3 , $1 - \rho = 0.17$), and the phosphate concentration (PO_4 , $1 - \rho = 0.15$).

5.1.3.2 Results for Benthic fauna models

We fitted the ensemble models for 339 species with acceptable performance, and found that all models generally performed well, with a mean (interquartile range across species) evaluation $AUC = 0.86$ (0.81; 0.90), $TSS = 0.62$ (0.55; 0.70), and $BOYCE = 0.81$ (0.68; 0.89). The ensemble models showed limited overfitting, with modest drops in the metrics between calibration and evaluation: $\Delta AUC = -0.02$ (-0.07; 0.01), $\Delta TSS = -0.01$ (-0.09; 0.06), and $\Delta BOYCE = -0.15$ (-0.27; -0.07). The most important variables were median temperature T_{median} , $1 - \rho = 0.17$ (0.07; 0.32); median oxygen $\text{O}_{2\text{median}}$, $1 - \rho = 0.12$

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(0.06; 0.26); median salinity SAL_{median} , $1-p = 0.07$ (0.04; 0.11); and minimum temperature T_{min} , $1-p = 0.07$ (0.02; 0.15).

5.1.3.3 Outlook

Modeling approaches provide a significant improvement with respect to existing information on benthic species based on sparse field sampling such as MEDITS, or on opportunistic datasets such as OBIS and GBIF. In fact, modeling approaches enable reconstructing the ecological niche of each species and using that information to build habitat suitability and biodiversity maps

5.1.4 Conclusions

The models were fitted using existing CMS data and will be fitted again using the new WP5 and WP6 products that will be available when we complete WP5 simulations. We expect the (already good) fitting capacity of the models to improve with the new products used as predictors.

Future development towards the final product will use information on average species density to generate maps of biomass at the sea bottom. This analysis will use species weight data available on MEDITS.

5.2 The Black Sea macrobenthos functions

5.2.1 Introduction

The biological community on the bottom of aquatic systems has an important impact on sediment geochemistry through their contribution to reaction (e.g. degradation of detritus and bacterial mediated chemical reactions) and to the transport of solutes (e.g. O_2 , NO_3^- , NH_4^+) and particles (e.g. organic matter, particulate metals) through bioirrigation and biomixing, respectively (Meysman et al., 2006). These transport processes play a key role in the structure and functioning of the subsurface ecosystem by modifying gradients of geochemical properties, redistributing food resources and affecting exchanges of material between the sediments and the overlaying water. However, so far, oceanic numerical models ignore the variability of life at the seafloor and its impact on biogeochemical cycles and ecosystem functioning (Snelgrove et al., 2018).

In this section, we describe our data sets combining species, traits, and abiotic data. We discuss results of multivariate analysis applied on these three tables through RLQ analysis and a fourth-corner matrix approach. Then, we provide spatial maps of multi-trait indicators (e.g. biomixing, bioirrigation) as a proxy for ecological functions delivered by the macrozoobenthos.

5.2.2 Material and Methods

5.2.2.1. Species collection

We compiled a set of 215 taxa of macrozoobenthos from 210 sampling stations collected between 2008 and 2017 over the northwestern shelf of the Black Sea (Figure 9). Sample collection used the same methodology as the standardized protocol in Todorova et al. (2005). Briefly, macrobenthos was sampled with a Van Veen grab with a surface of 0.135 m^2 and washed through a 0.5 mm mesh sieve. In the laboratory, the organisms were counted and identified to the lowest possible taxonomic level. Individual organism density was expressed in number of individuals per m^2 and were $\log_{10}(x + 1)$ transformed to down-scale large values.

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Figure 9: The Black Sea. Named rivers provide the main sources of freshwater inputs; black dots represent the sampling stations from 2008 to 2017. Contour lines and colour bar denote water depth in meters.

5.2.2.2. Abiotic data

Abiotic conditions were characterized from *in-situ* data (i.e. sampling depth, substratum type) and from the coupled hydrodynamical-biogeochemical NEMO42 – BAMHBI model run in reanalysis mode at a resolution of 2.5 km with 59 vertical levels (for more details on the model see Grégoire et al., 2025; Capet et al., 2016; Grégoire et al., 2008; Grégoire and Soetaert (2010)). Our list focuses on a variety of environmental variables expected to influence the distribution of indicators of ecological processes, including bottom dissolved oxygen, flux of particulate organic carbon to the sediment, bottom shear stress, and substratum type. A complete list of abiotic drivers is provided in Table 8. We derived mean, maximum, minimum, and standard deviation for each abiotic variable at three different time scales: trimestral and annual scales centred around the date of the sampling and from a 10-years climatology covering the full data collection period (i.e. 2008-2018).

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Table 8: List of abiotic predictors derived from the coupled hydrodynamical-biogeochemical NEMO4.2-BAMBHI model or from in-situ sampling, including their respective abbreviation and unit.

Abiotic descriptors	Abbreviation	Unit
Model variables		
Bottom temperature	TEMP	°C
Bottom thermal seasonality	TEMPCV	-
Bottom Salinity	SAL	p.s.u (practical salinity unit)
Bottom shear stress	SHEAR	N m ⁻²
Bottom photosynthetically active radiation	PAR	W m ⁻²
Bottom Particulate organic carbon content	POC	mmol C m ⁻³
Vertically integrated sedimentary organic carbon concentration (fast decay)	fCSED	mmol C m ⁻²
Vertically integrated sedimentary organic carbon concentration (slow decay)	sCSED	mmol C m ⁻²
Bottom dissolved oxygen concentration	DOX	μmol l ⁻¹
Bottom Dissolved oxygen seasonality	DOXCV	-
Particulate organic carbon flux to the bottom	botfluxPOC	mmol C m ⁻² day ⁻¹
In-situ variables		
In-situ depth	Depth	m
Type of substratum	SUBSTRATUM	Factor with 3 levels: 1) Muddy to sandy mud 2) Sandy to muddy sand 3) Coarse and mixed

5.2.2.3. Traits compilation

In NECCTON, we documented 27 traits for 127 taxa that related to life cycle (e.g. annual fecundity, offspring development) and ecosystem function (e.g. burrowing depth, mobility). Each trait was divided into several modalities representing either intervals along a gradient or qualitative states. When a taxon had clearly an affinity for one or more modalities, we assigned 1 for the corresponding modalities and 0 everywhere else. When information was not available at the species level, we considered information at the genus level. For estimating macrozoobenthos functions, we selected effect traits with an impact on sediment mixing and nutrients cycling (Table 9).

Table 9: List of selected effect traits with their units, abbreviation, modalities, definitions, and modality-score that gives the contribution of the modality to the intensity of the selected ecological processes.

Trait [Units] (Abbreviation)	Modality	Definition	Modality-scores
Body Mass [g AFDM] (BM)	<0.001	Body size, amount of living tissues. Proxy for metabolic demand.	1
	0.001-0.010		2
	0.010-0.100		3
	0.100-1.000		4
	1.000-10.000		5
	>10.000		6
Feeding type [\] (FT)	Deposit feeding (De)		1
	Suspension feeding (Su)		1

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	Herbivory/Grazing (HeGr)	Informs on food resource origin and how organic matter is processed.	1
	Carnivory/Scavenging (CaSc)		1
Substratum depth occupancy [cm] (SD)	0	Occupied layers of the sediment.	1
	0-5		2
	5-15		3
	15-30		4
	>30		5
Mobility [\] (MB)	Immobile	Dwelling mode, metabolic demand, and species interactive potential.	0
	Limited		1
	Slow		2
	Fast		3
	Very fast		4
Sediment mixing type [\] (AF)	None	Type of sediment particle displacement. Diffusion, random, local. Conveying, vertical, non-local. Regeneration, Instantaneous downward transfer (e.g. large burrow collapse).	0
	Diffusion		1
	Upward conveying		1
	Downward conveying		1
	Regeneration		1
Ventilation/Pumping [\] (VP)	Null	Ability to flush water into a burrow.	1
	Low		2
	High		3
Endo-bioconstruction type [\] (BT)	None	Biogenic structure built in the sediment; Closed, only one opening. Opened, U- or Y-shaped burrow, possibly more than two openings.	1
	Blind-ended		2
	Open-ended		3
Endo-bioconstruction depth [cm] (maxBD)	None/Surficial	Size of endo-bioconstruction (e.g., depth of a burrow).	0
	0-5		1
	5-15		2
	15-30		3
	>30		4

5.2.2.4. Multi-traits-based indicators

We estimated the contribution of each species to an ecological process based on indicators (i.e. a trait derived from a formula incorporating several traits; Beauchard et al., 2017). Here, we chose the indicators defined in Beauchard et al (2023) for four ecological processes that play a key role in the mediation of the benthic-pelagic coupling: biomixing, bioirrigation, biodeposition, and deposit feeding (Table 10). After scaling each multi-trait-based indicator from 0 to 1, we derived community-level indicators (i.e. matrix sampling sites x indicators) by summing over all the species of the community the potential of individual species weighted by their individual densities (i.e. number of individuals of a species).

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Table 10: Indicators of ecological process for a species n , definition and formula. n is the total number of species and i refers to the four modes of sediment mixing type. Details on each trait used in formula can be found in Table 9.

Indicator	Definition	Formula
Biomixing (mi)	One of the two process of bioturbation through particle reworking (Kristensen et al., 2012)	$mi(n) = \sum_{i=1}^4 AF(n, i) * BM(n) * MB(n) * SD(n)$
Bioirrigation (ir)	One of the two process of bioturbation through ventilation (Kristensen et al., 2012)	$ir(n) = VP(n) * BM(n) * maxBD(n)$
Biodeposition (de)	Benthic-pelagic transfer through suspension feeding (Graf and Rosenberg, 1997)	$de(n) = BM(n) * Su(n)$
Deposit feeding (Dep)	Ingestion of large volumes of sediment (Lopez and Levinton, 1987)	$Dep(n) = BM(n) * De(n)$

5.2.2.5. Local Trait-Environment relationships

We used a RLQ analysis in combination with the fourth-corner approach to identify the environmental variables that correlated significantly with traits or indicators (Dray et al., 2003; Dray et al., 2014; Legendre et al., 1997). Briefly, the RLQ analysis is a three-tables ordination that aims to link environmental conditions (i.e. matrix R) with species traits (i.e. matrix L) through species occurrence table (i.e. matrix L). Before the RLQ analysis, we applied separate univariate analyses on the three tables : a multiple correspondence analysis (MCA) on environmental matrix R (as in Chevalier et al. (2024) using qualitative abiotic data to circumvent non-linearities); a correspondence Analysis (CoA) on the species table L, and a fuzzy correspondence analysis (FCA) to the fuzzy-coded trait data matrix (Q) or principal component analysis (PCA) for quantitative indicators. Separate analyses of traits and environmental variables were weighted respectively by the species and sites weights derived from the CoA (Dray and Dufour, 2007).

Then, we tested the correlations between RLQ axes and individual traits or abiotic conditions to improve the interpretation of the RLQ results (see more details in Dray et al., 2014). A graphical summary of RLQ analysis is provided in Figure 10. The RLQ and fourth-corner analyses were performed using the ade4 package for R software (Dray and Dufour, 2007).

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Figure 10: Schematic representation of the data set. Block arrows indicate how matrices (rectangles) match each other (i.e., either by the same number of rows or columns). Single ordination techniques are applied on the three tables (from 1 to 3), double arrows (4 and 5) are for the ordination of two tables. These five multivariate analyses are summarized through RLQ and Fourth-corner analysis (6). Figure adapted from Dolédec et al. (1996).

5.2.3 Results and Discussion

5.2.3.1. RLQ analysis results

We applied a RLQ analysis on the effect traits used to compute multi-traits based indicators (Table 11). The RLQ analysis demonstrated a significant global correlation between traits and environmental variables. The first axis of the RLQ correlates significantly with substratum type as well as the two traits burrowing depth and ventilation/pumping (Figure 11). The second axis correlates with ventilation/pumping trait and salinity, with the highest ventilation ability at low salinity. The total RLQ (axis 1 and 2) also correlates with the same combinations of abiotic conditions and traits (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Left: Habitat descriptor- Q axis significance. Right: traits-R axis significance. “SD” refers to the trait substratum occupancy depth and “VP” to the ventilation/pumping trait. Color bar for significance at the right (white cells meaning no significant relationships).

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The first axis of the RLQ analysis explains 67% of the cross-covariance between traits and environment. It separates mixed-coarse substratum at intermediate to high salinity (negative values on the first axis of the RLQ, Figure 11 at the left) from the finer substratum type at low to intermediate salinity (positive values on the first axis of the RLQ, Figure 11 at the left). The first axis separates epibenthos with no ventilation/pumping ability at mixed coarse-grained sites from endobenthic species with ventilation/pumping ability (Figure 12 at the right). The second axis accounts for 32% of the variability and separates sandy substratum at very low salinity sites with higher ventilation pumping and deeper burrowing species (deeper than 15 cm) from muddier substratum with lower ventilation ability and shallower burrowing depth (Figure 13).

Figure 12: Left, abiotic descriptors scores on the first axis of the RLQ (black) and second axis of the RLQ (red). Right: modalities scores. For the traits, “null”, “low” and “high” correspond to the three modalities of the trait ventilation/pumping and from “0” to “>30” to the five modalities of the trait substratum depth occupancy.

We then performed the same RLQ combined with fourth-corner analysis on the four indicators. The RLQ analysis does not show a significant global correlation between traits and environmental variables. However, we found significant correlations between the first axis of the RLQ and a salinity gradient with low salinity at very shallow sites (i.e. lower than 20 m) associated with high bioirrigation and deposit feeding intensity.

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Figure 13: Left: abiotic descriptors scores on the first axis of the RLQ (black). Right: indicators scores (De = deposit feeding and ir = bioirrigation).

5.2.3.2. Spatial distribution of ecological indicators

We mapped the potential distribution of the four indicators at shelf scale using Gaussian process regression (Figure 14). We found high positive correlation between ecological processes at a community level and key characteristics of macrozoobenthic communities (species diversity and number of individuals). At the edge of the shelf, reduced abundance and biomass of the macrozoobenthic communities reflect upwellings of euxinic water and the very low values of the potential of biomixing and bioirrigation as low- oxygen conditions inhibit bioturbation activity. The biomixing, bioirrigation and deposit feeding potential of the community share a similar spatial pattern over the shelf with higher intensity of ecological processes at shallower depth and in the Danube delta front area (Figure 14) that match the RLQ analysis as higher intensities of bioirrigation and deposit-feeding link to very shallow low salinity sites. Mostly fine mud associated with deeper burrow and higher ventilation/pumping activities close to the mouth of the Danube compared to the coarse-grained substratum as previously noted by the RLQ and fourth-corner analyses. We did not find any significant relationships between biodepositon and abiotic conditions with multivariate analysis, but observe hotspot of biodeposition near the Dnieper River delta in the north-east sector, in the coastal southern of the shelf up to more than 50 m.

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Figure 14: Mapping of the four ecological indicators at the scale of the northwestern shelf of the Black Sea. From top right to bottom left panel: biodeposition, deposit feeding, biomixing, and bioirrigation potential of the community. Continuous lines indicate contours of the bathymetry. Color bar at the right indicates the intensity of ecological processes (from dark yellow to dark blue meaning higher intensity).

5.2.4 Conclusions

In the framework of NECTON, we published a first paper linking organic pollution and macrozoobenthos communities between 1995 and 2008-2017 periods (Chevalier et al., 2024). Then, we submitted a data paper combining traits, macrobenthos species, and abiotic conditions in Scientific Data (in review); we work in closed collaboration with our Romanian and Bulgarian co-authors who collected and processed macrozoobenthos samples. This data set aims to fill the functional knowledge gap in the Black Sea and offers research opportunities to future studies addressing ecosystem functions, biodiversity conservation, and management in the Black Sea.

We next aim to publish a third paper linking abiotic conditions and traits through multivariate statistics and providing maps of relevant traits or multi-traits-based indicators. We demonstrated that

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distribution of traits is not random across the shelf and can be partially explained by a depth-gradient, the type of substratum type for substratum depth occupancy (used for building the biomixing indicator), and ventilation/pumping ability (used for bioirrigation indicator). However, we found a limited number of significant relationships between macrozoobenthic traits and abiotic conditions that may arise from the spatial mismatch between environmental drivers (2.5 km) and macrobenthic species (grab samples at the scale of less than 1 m²). As a next step we will improve traits maps with machine-learning based model (i.e. Artificial Neural Networks). We will use knowledge gained from our multivariate analysis to build trait distribution models for a select set of traits and indicators. The final step of our work will introduce the influence of seafloor life by extending current parameterizations of benthic processes (e.g. sediment mixing length, constant mixing coefficient) to consider the effect of variation in marine life deduced from the analysis of traits maps. This work aims to improve the representation of the water-sediment interface and benthic-pelagic coupling in large scale ocean modelling.

5.3 The Black Sea seaweeds and mussels (NIOZ)

5.3.1 Introduction

Mussel beds and seaweed forests are essential for the functioning of some benthic systems. Often referred to as ‘ecosystem engineers’, these species create specific biogenic habitats that can be very productive and crucial to the cycling of nutrients. Besides their effects on benthic systems, mussel beds and seaweed forests are also critical for pelagic fish populations in that they harbour juveniles and provide important food web connections. These functions underscore the crucial importance of protecting and understanding these biogenic structures, because they many anthropogenic pressures such as eutrophication from river runoffs and damage by bottom trawling threaten them. Protecting these habitats and predicting their dynamics is non-trivial, therefore underscoring the importance of a solid understanding of processes driving growth and distribution. To assist in the understanding of growth and distribution of benthic keystone species, we have developed dynamic biochemical process models that describe and predict growth of mussels and seaweed in the Black Sea. These models were developed based on several state-of-the-art theories and models from the literature, such as dynamic energy budget (DEB) theory (Kooijman, 2010). For the Black Sea, the benthic process models were developed by specifically modelling keystone species. The mussel beds were modelled based on the distinct mussel species occurring in the Black Sea, the Mediterranean mussel *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, for which we modelled individual growth and population dynamics. For macroalgae, we are developing a model that captures growth of the two keystone species that resemble the two most common seaweed assemblages: *Cystoseira spp.* and *Phyllophora spp.* All models will be published in R software packages, with parameter sets specifically calibrated on the described species (R Core Team, 2022).

5.3.2 Material and Methods

Model concept: Black Sea macroalgae

The Black Sea macroalgae model is still in development but the conceptual framework is mostly ready (Figure 15). The model will focus on the 2 main seaweed Black Sea species: *Phyllophora crispata* & *Cystoseira barbata*. Physiologically, susceptibility to different wavelengths of light defines one of the

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core differences between these species and their assemblages (Luning & Dring, 1985). As wavelength generalists, brown algae, such as *Cystoseira*, have a similar susceptibility for all wavelengths in the PAR spectrum (400-700nm). In contrast, red seaweeds, such as *Phyllophora*, have a clearly lower capacity to utilize longer wavelengths (600-700 nm) which attenuate quicker with depth. This difference results in generally deeper habitat distributions for red seaweeds that can utilize wavelengths that travel deeper into the water. Besides light attenuation, the model includes nitrogen uptake, temperature, and oxygen as environmental factors.

Figure 15: Schematic model of Black Sea macroalgae physiology. The macroalgae model will consider different attenuation between short (400-500 nm) middle (500-600) and long (600-700) wavelengths, and will model oxygen and nutrients based on forcing timeseries and a simple dilution rate for exchange between local and forced dissolved values.

Model description: Black Sea mussels

For the individual physiology of mussels, we developed a carbon-based DEB model with an additional filter feeder module that captures multiple food types. The feeding module was originally derived by Saraiva et al., (2011), which we simplified slightly to fit with NEMO-BAMHBI outputs. The mussel model encompasses two parts, the first is the DEB growth model based on individual physiology, the second is the expansion of this model with population dynamics (Figure 16). The population model is constructed from several cohorts of average individuals that are determined by the individual model. Population dynamics, birth and death, follow from the sum of individual reproduction events and the resulting larval dynamics, in the case of birth, and follow from stressors of individual growth, in case of mortality. The DEB variables define the state variables that are explicitly followed in the individual model: functional structure, energy reserves and reproduction buffer. The population model also

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includes the state variables density, divided into several cohorts of mussels, and larvae specific biomass and density (Table 11). As environmental factors that determine growth, we included food, temperature, oxygen, and inorganic suspended materials (Table 13). We divide food into two organic particle types, phytoplankton, an efficient food source and detritus, a less efficient food source.

Figure 16: Schematic model of mussel physiology and population dynamics

Table 11: State variables of *M. galloprovincialis* DEB models

State variable	Description	Unit	Model type
STRUCTURE	Structural carbon of individual	mmol C/ind	Individual
RESERVE	Energy reserves of individual	mmol C/ind	Individual
REPRODUCTION	Energy contained in gonads & gametes	mmol C/ind	Individual
POPULATION	Number of individuals in cohort	ind/m ²	Population
LARVA BIOMASS	Larval biomass concentration	mmol C/m ³	Population
LARVA DENSITY	Larval population density	ind/m ³	Population

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Table 12: Main processes in the *M. galloprovincialis* models. Processes that have specific rates for multiple particle types have an asterisk (*). Processes that are developed in the current project are referred to as 'NECCTON', processes that are based on DEB theory are referred to as 'DEB'.

Process	Associated rates	Short description	Model	Reference
Seawater clearance	Clearance rate, Filtration rate*	Amount of seawater cleared, and particles filtered.	Ind	Saraiva et al., 2011
Ingestion	Pseudofeces flux*, Ingestion rate*	Filtered particles ingested and excreted.	Ind	Saraiva et al., 2011
Assimilation	Assimilation of C, Feceation	Ingested carbon assimilated or excreted.	Ind	NECCTON
Catabolism	Energy utilisation	Rate of reserve utilization	Ind	DEB
Respiration	Structural maintenance, Reproduction maintenance, Regression, Rejuvenation	Basal maintenance to be paid by utilisation flux, if utilisation is not sufficient, maintenance will be paid by reproductive biomass (rejuvenation) or structural biomass (regression).	Ind	DEB
Growth	Structural growth	Growth of structural biomass	Ind	DEB
Reproduction	Gonad development, Gamete development, Spawning	Growth of gonad & gamete biomass. Release of stored gametes during spawning events.	Ind	DEB, NECCTON
Larval dynamics	Larva growth, larva mortality	Larva per capita mortality and biomass specific growth	Pop	NECCTON
Cohort spawning	Settling rate	Full grown larvae develop into a new cohort of mussels	Pop	NECCTON
Population mortality	Basal mortality rate, crowding mortality, starvation mortality, size mortality	Per capita mortality rate combines multiple factors. Environmental factors affect mortality through starvation of an average individual.	Pop	NECCTON

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Table 13: Environmental forcings that drive the dynamics of the *M. galloprovincialis* models.

Environmental forcing	Units	Affected processes
Temperature	Degree Celsius	Clearance, catabolism, maintenance
Oxygen	mmol[O ₂]/ m ³	Clearance, maintenance
Phytoplankton	mmol[C]/m ³	Clearance, ingestion, assimilation
Detritus	mmol[C]/m ³	Clearance, ingestion, assimilation
Suspended Inorganic Matter	g/m ³	Clearance, ingestion

Model behaviour

At its core, the model functions as a typical DEB model, in which individuals grow to an asymptotic size under a constant environment. Forced with near-optimal constant environmental factors, the current parametrization reaches an asymptotic size of around 15 cm shell length (Figure 17a), which is consistent with the maximum observed shell length of *M. galloprovincialis*. Both structural and reserve carbon pools also increase towards an asymptote. The reproduction buffer consists of gonads and gametes. The gonads grow towards a certain value where they reach maturity, and from this moment, all energy put into the reproduction buffer is turned into gametes. The gamete pool empties twice per year, because we assume a spring and an autumn spawning (Figure 17, bc). All gametes are released during each spawning, only the reproduction baseline, determined by the gonad biomass (approximately 3 mmol Carbon/ind) is not released (Figure 17, d).

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Figure 17: The development of the individual model shown by the 3 state variables: structure, reserve, and reproduction. Additionally, the figure shows the main derived output variable, length. The current model is run for 3 years, with a constant environment of 100 mmol/m³ phytoplankton, 10 mmolC/m³ detritus, 20 degrees Celsius, 360 mmol O₂/m³ and 1 g/l suspended inorganic matter.

In DEB theory, environmental temperature and food concentration always affect the energy balance of an individual. Because food concentration provides the main source of energy in the model, increased food concentration increases asymptotic size and reproduction output (figure 17). However, because we have separated food into two types, an increase in the main food source (phytoplankton) has greater impact than a similar increase in the secondary food source (detritus). Increasing temperature increases the rates of physiological processes (table 12). A constant increase in temperature decreases asymptotic size, because the respiration increase has a greater impact on size than the foraging (clearance) increase. However, reproductive output remains higher in a high temperature environment because gametes have no respiration cost in the model (figure 18).

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Figure 18: The development of the individual model shown by the 3 state variables: structure, reserve and reproduction and length under different constant environmental conditions. HtHf = high temperature high food, HtLf = high temperature low food, LtHf = low temperature high food, LtLf = low temperature low food.

The *M. galloprovincialis* population model shows similar dynamics as the individual model for each separate cohort. However, competition between conspecifics in the population model drastically decreases the available food for individuals and therefore reduces growth potential for all individuals. Each year, 2 spawning periods determine the amount of carbon released as gametes, which is recalculated as the number of larvae to add to the larva density and biomass pools. Mortality affects larval density, and concentration has a biomass specific growth that is affected by phytoplankton and temperature. These dynamics result in decreasing larval density and an increasing larva individual biomass. When individual biomass exceeds a threshold, the larvae are defined as suitable pediveligers, and they start to settle with a maximum settling rate. Settled larvae are put into the density pool of a new cohort, and each wave of larvae is put into its own cohort, which follows its own individual DEB dynamics (which is defined as the average individual). The resulting population dynamics slowly converge to semi-stable population that remain between an upper and lower bound (Figure 19). Fluctuating forcings, or one-way model coupling results in more erratic model behaviour.

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Figure 19: Example model runs of the *M. galloprovincialis* population model. Models are run for 15 years to show the eventual seasonal stability. Model forcings are non-dynamic and constant, without competition for resources. Four different sets of forcings are provided, black lines have both high food (10 mmolC/m³ phytoplankton) and high temperature (20dgC). Red lines are forced with high temperature and low food (5 mmolC/m³). Runs with constant low temperature (5 dggC) are not viable, regardless of food conditions (green and blue lines overlap). This outcome results from larval mortality outpacing larval growth in permanently cold environments.

Calibration and Validation of mussel growth model

Calibration and validation of the mussel growth model use datasets on individual *Mytilus galloprovincialis* growth from literature. Physiological growth parameters were all retrieved from published DEB models and feeding parameters were calibrated based on individual growth data on Black Sea mussels retrieved from publications: Karayucel et al. (2010), Vural et al. (2015) (figure 20). Validation of individual growth was performed by comparing model runs, forced with NEMO-BAMHBI derived environmental timeseries, with the growth curve derived from Chelyadina & Popov (2020) (figure 21). Additionally, we compared some physiological rates with experimentally derived rates from Galimany et al., (2015) (figure 20).

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Figure 20: Length and biomass data from Sinop (Karayucel et al., 2010), top panels, and Dardanelles (Vural et al., 2015), bottom panel. Model runs are shown with 10 % variation in feeding parameters. These datasets were used to calibrate feeding parameters of the Saraiva et al., (2011) filter feeding module.

Figure 21: Points show growth data from Chelyadina & Popov (2020). Lines show model runs at the same location, temperature, extracted from the same publication, whereas other environmental variables were extracted from NEMO-BAMHBI at the same location and time. Data were not used for calibration and plots are only meant to validate the individual growth model predictions.

5.3.3 Results and Discussion

We used the developed model in a one-way offline coupling with NEMO-BAMHBI model data of the Black Sea. The model coupling can be used to analyse growth potential, reproduction success and estimate populations in the Black Sea during all years for which NEMO-BAMHBI was run. Here, we

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report the predicted growth potential associated with the Black Sea hindcast from 2000 to 2019 (figure 22). Growth potential should be interpreted as the maximal potential size that an individual in that region could reach without any biological interactions such as competition with conspecifics or predation. We extracted the environmental timeseries from bottom data. The results clearly shows the division between the deep anoxic and shelf sea areas of the Black Sea, and note that the northwestern shelf in particular has many regions that show good potential for mussel growth.

Figure 22: Shell length after 3 years of growth without competition.

5.3.4 Conclusions

To conclude, development of the Black Sea *Mytilus galloprovincialis* model has almost concluded. The model parameters, except for the population dynamics module, were validated against field data from the Black Sea. Running the model to calculate growth potential in the Black Sea from 2000 to 2019 showed a clear dichotomy between the deep anoxic part of the Black Sea basin and the productive shelf seas. Generally, the closer to the coast, the higher the potential growth, likely reflecting elevated phytoplankton growth promoted by river runoffs.

The Seaweed model is currently still under construction. Assessing where the *Phyllophora* assemblage can grow, as opposed to the *Cystoseira* assemblage is possible with this model. However, the exact growth parameters still requires calibration and validation. This model can be used to determine the future deterioration of the famous Zernov *Phyllophora* field, related to increased turbidity in eutrophicated waters.

To date, benthic biological process models have been developed and tested to be run in isolation (offline). The model does not consider certain ecological feedback of the currently developed models, such as mussel filtration of particulates or seaweed nutrient uptake processes to the environment. In the future, a two-way coupling between these models the environmental biogeochemistry (BAHMBI) will be possible to analyse this feedback mechanism.

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6 Conclusions

In this document, we have described a set of new processes that have been implemented in a suite of different biogeochemical models and tested in different environments. The processes have been tested in isolation. In future work within NECCTON, we will combine them and run them together, and quantify their impact on simulation quality. The validation of the modelling modules described in this deliverable will be described in a subsequent deliverable (Deliverable 9.1).

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Table S1 – List of species used to fit the models. The field AphiaID refers to the Aphia code from the Darwin Core Standard. The field npoints is the number of points used to fit the models.

ID	Phylum	Class	Order	Family	Name	AphiaID	npoints
1	Annelida	Polychaeta		Capitellidae	<i>Heteromastus filiformis</i>	129884	153
2	Annelida	Polychaeta		Capitellidae	<i>Notomastus latericeus</i>	129898	180
3	Annelida	Polychaeta		Oweniidae	<i>Myriochele heeri</i>	130542	124
4	Annelida	Polychaeta		Oweniidae	<i>Owenia fusiformis</i>	130544	177
5	Annelida	Polychaeta	Amphinomida	Amphinomidae	<i>Hermodice carunculata</i>	129831	279
6	Annelida	Polychaeta	Echiuroidea	Bonelliidae	<i>Bonellia viridis</i>	110363	272
7	Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Eunicidae	<i>Eunice vittata</i>	130067	164
8	Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Lumbrineridae	<i>Lumbrineris latreilli</i>	130248	283
9	Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Oeonidae	<i>Drilonereis filum</i>	129856	137
10	Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Onuphidae	<i>Aponuphis bilineata</i>	130452	123
11	Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Onuphidae	<i>Hyalinoecia tubicola</i>	130464	231
12	Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Aphroditidae	<i>Aphrodita aculeata</i>	129840	487
13	Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Aphroditidae	<i>Laetmonice hystrix</i>	129845	137
14	Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Glyceridae	<i>Glycera alba</i>	130116	157
15	Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Glyceridae	<i>Glycera tridactyla</i>	130130	122
16	Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Glyceridae	<i>Glycera unicornis</i>	130131	195
17	Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Goniadidae	<i>Goniada maculata</i>	130140	201
18	Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Nephtyidae	<i>Nephtys hombergii</i>	130359	144
19	Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Sigalionidae	<i>Sigalion mathildae</i>	131072	122
20	Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Sabellidae	<i>Sabella pavonina</i>	130967	221
21	Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Sabellidae	<i>Sabella spallanzanii</i>	130969	478
22	Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Serpulidae	<i>Protula intestinum</i>	131032	175
23	Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Serpulidae	<i>Protula tubularia</i>	131035	364
24	Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Serpulidae	<i>Serpula vermicularis</i>	131051	287
25	Annelida	Polychaeta	Spionida	Spionidae	<i>Laonice cirrata</i>	131128	127
26	Annelida	Polychaeta	Spionida	Spionidae	<i>Prionospio steenstrupi</i>	131164	135
27	Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Ampharetidae	<i>Ampharete grubei</i>	152272	132

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ID	Phylum	Class	Order	Family	Name	AphiaID	npoints
28	Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Melinnidae	<i>Melinna palmata</i>	129808	148
29	Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Sternaspidae	<i>Sternaspis scutata</i>	131242	258
30	Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Terebellidae	<i>Eupolymnia nebulosa</i>	131489	173
31	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Ampeliscidae	<i>Ampelisca sarsi</i>	101923	137
32	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Ampeliscidae	<i>Ampelisca typica</i>	101933	156
33	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Alpheidae	<i>Alpheus glaber</i>	107477	929
34	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Alpheidae	<i>Athanas nitescens</i>	107486	155
35	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Axiidae	<i>Calocaris macandreae</i>	107726	276
36	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Calappidae	<i>Calappa granulata</i>	107268	504
37	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Cambaridae	<i>Procambarus clarkii</i>	465540	148
38	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Carcinidae	<i>Carcinus aestuarii</i>	107380	219
39	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Crangonidae	<i>Aegaeon cataphractus</i>	107548	442
40	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Crangonidae	<i>Aegaeon lacazei</i>	107549	757
41	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Crangonidae	<i>Philocheras echinulatus</i>	107558	183
42	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Crangonidae	<i>Pontophilus spinosus</i>	107564	600
43	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Diogenidae	<i>Calcinus tubularis</i>	107194	206
44	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Diogenidae	<i>Clibanarius erythropus</i>	107196	547
45	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Diogenidae	<i>Dardanus arrosor</i>	107197	1664
46	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Diogenidae	<i>Dardanus calidus</i>	107198	373
47	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Diogenidae	<i>Diogenes pugilator</i>	107199	323
48	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Diogenidae	<i>Paguristes eremita</i>	107200	170
49	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Dorippidae	<i>Medorippe lanata</i>	107288	882
50	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Dromiidae	<i>Dromia personata</i>	107258	301
51	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Epialtidae	<i>Pisa armata</i>	107353	219
52	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Eriphiidae	<i>Eriphia verrucosa</i>	107409	703
53	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Ethusidae	<i>Ethusa mascarone</i>	107283	136
54	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Galatheididae	<i>Galathea intermedia</i>	107150	171
55	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Galatheididae	<i>Galathea strigosa</i>	107155	186

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56	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Geryonidae	<i>Geryon longipes</i>	107373	789
57	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Goneplacidae	<i>Goneplax rhomboides</i>	107292	1325
58	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Grapsidae	<i>Pachygrapsus marmoratus</i>	107455	1001
59	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Homolidae	<i>Homola barbata</i>	107262	180
60	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Homolidae	<i>Paromola cuvieri</i>	107264	689
61	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Inachidae	<i>Inachus communissimus</i>	107326	127
62	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Inachidae	<i>Inachus dorsettensis</i>	107327	432
63	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Inachidae	<i>Inachus phalangium</i>	107333	145
64	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Inachidae	<i>Inachus thoracicus</i>	107334	221
65	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Inachidae	<i>Macropodia linaresi</i>	107341	121
66	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Inachidae	<i>Macropodia longirostris</i>	107343	126
67	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Inachidae	<i>Macropodia rostrata</i>	107345	266
68	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Inachidae	<i>Macropodia tenuirostris</i>	107346	910
69	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Latreillidae	<i>Latreillia elegans</i>	107265	252
70	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Lysmatidae	<i>Lysmata seticaudata</i>	107528	152
71	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Majidae	<i>Maja crispata</i>	107348	371
72	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Majidae	<i>Maja squinado</i>	107350	321
73	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Munididae	<i>Munida intermedia</i>	107157	807
74	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Munididae	<i>Munida tenuimana</i>	107166	247
75	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Munididae	<i>Iridonida speciosa</i>	1606714	512
76	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Nephropidae	<i>Homarus gammarus</i>	107253	189
77	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Paguridae	<i>Pagurus alatus</i>	107230	730
78	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Paguridae	<i>Pagurus anachoretus</i>	107231	306
79	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Paguridae	<i>Pagurus cuanensis</i>	107235	264
80	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Paguridae	<i>Pagurus excavatus</i>	107236	750
81	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Paguridae	<i>Pagurus prideaux</i>	107239	757
82	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Palaemonidae	<i>Palaemon elegans</i>	107614	405
83	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Palaemonidae	<i>Palaemon serratus</i>	107616	168

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84	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Palinuridae	<i>Palinurus elephas</i>	107703	756
85	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Pandalidae	<i>Chlorotocus crassicornis</i>	107642	1326
86	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Pandalidae	<i>Plesionika acanthonotus</i>	107654	881
87	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Pandalidae	<i>Plesionika antigai</i>	107655	604
88	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Pandalidae	<i>Plesionika edwardsii</i>	107656	645
89	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Pandalidae	<i>Plesionika giglioli</i>	107659	1099
90	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Pandalidae	<i>Plesionika heterocarpus</i>	107660	1598
91	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Pandalidae	<i>Plesionika martia</i>	107661	1650
92	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Pandalidae	<i>Plesionika narval</i>	107662	272
93	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Parthenopidae	<i>Spinolambrus macrochelos</i>	442337	266
94	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Penaeidae	<i>Penaeus kerathurus</i>	246388	178
95	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Pilumnidae	<i>Pilumnus hirtellus</i>	107418	167
96	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Pilumnidae	<i>Pilumnus spinifer</i>	107420	269
97	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Pilumnidae	<i>Pilumnus villosissimus</i>	107421	132
98	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Polybiidae	<i>Bathynectes maravigna</i>	107377	494
99	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Polybiidae	<i>Polybius vernalis</i>	1750288	151
100	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Polybiidae	<i>Polybius depurator</i>	1750291	1953
101	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Polybiidae	<i>Macropipus tuberculatus</i>	107397	1528
102	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Polychelidae	<i>Polycheles typhlops</i>	107696	1371
103	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Porcellanidae	<i>Pisidia longicornis</i>	107188	130
104	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Processidae	<i>Processa canaliculata</i>	107682	751
105	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Processidae	<i>Processa nouveli</i>	107689	247
106	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Scyllaridae	<i>Scyllarides latus</i>	107708	179
107	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Scyllaridae	<i>Scyllarus arctus</i>	107709	185
108	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Solenoceridae	<i>Solenocera membranacea</i>	107120	1614
109	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Stenopodidae	<i>Stenopus spinosus</i>	107721	135
110	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Xanthidae	<i>Monodaeus couchii</i>	241154	549
111	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Xanthidae	<i>Xantho poressa</i>	107442	138

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112	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Cirolanidae	<i>Natanolana borealis</i>	118859	128
113	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Stomatopoda	Squillidae	<i>Rissoides pallidus</i>	136136	201
114	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Stomatopoda	Squillidae	<i>Squilla mantis</i>	136137	1074
115	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Tanaidacea	Apeudidae	<i>Apeudopsis latreillii</i>	247077	135
116	Arthropoda	Thecostraca	Scalpellomorpha	Scalpellidae	<i>Scalpellum scalpellum</i>	106204	321
117	Brachiopoda	Rhynchonellata	Terebratulida	Terebratulidae	<i>Gryphus vitreus</i>	104068	344
118	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Adeonidae	<i>Adeonella calveti</i>	111055	144
119	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Adeonidae	<i>Reptadeonella violacea</i>	111061	132
120	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Bitectiporidae	<i>Pentapora fascialis</i>	111082	253
121	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Bitectiporidae	<i>Schizomavella (Schizomavella) mamillata</i>	862797	129
122	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Electridae	<i>Electra posidoniae</i>	111356	155
123	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Myriaporidae	<i>Myriapora truncata</i>	111435	390
124	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Phidoloporidae	<i>Reteporella grimaldii</i>	111453	222
125	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Phidoloporidae	<i>Reteporella mediterranea</i>	1041728	123
126	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Schizoporellidae	<i>Schizobrachiella sanguinea</i>	111522	170
127	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Smittinidae	<i>Smittina cervicornis</i>	111551	180
128	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Aplousobranchia	Clavelinidae	<i>Clavelina lepadiformis</i>	103552	190
129	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Aplousobranchia	Diazonidae	<i>Diazona violacea</i>	103733	311
130	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Aplousobranchia	Polyclinidae	<i>Aplidium conicum</i>	103641	227
131	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Aplousobranchia	Polyclinidae	<i>Aplidium elegans</i>	103643	127
132	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Phlebobranchia	Asciidiidae	<i>Ascidia mentula</i>	103710	656
133	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Phlebobranchia	Asciidiidae	<i>Ascidia virginea</i>	103717	267
134	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Phlebobranchia	Asciidiidae	<i>Asciidiella aspersa</i>	103718	136
135	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Phlebobranchia	Asciidiidae	<i>Asciidiella scabra</i>	103719	172
136	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Phlebobranchia	Asciidiidae	<i>Phallusia mammillata</i>	103724	740
137	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Phlebobranchia	Cionidae	<i>Ciona intestinalis</i>	103732	163
138	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Stolidobranchia	Molgulidae	<i>Molgula appendiculata</i>	103771	144
139	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Stolidobranchia	Pyuridae	<i>Halocynthia papillosa</i>	103827	551

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140	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Stolidobranchia	Pyuridae	<i>Microcosmus sabatieri</i>	103844	231
141	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Stolidobranchia	Pyuridae	<i>Microcosmus vulgaris</i>	103846	351
142	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Stolidobranchia	Styelidae	<i>Botryllus schlosseri</i>	103862	278
143	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Actiniaria	Actiniidae	<i>Actinia mediterranea</i>	854459	545
144	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Actiniaria	Actiniidae	<i>Anemonia viridis</i>	100808	587
145	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Actiniaria	Actiniidae	<i>Cribrinopsis crassa</i>	100823	167
146	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Actiniaria	Aiptasiidae	<i>Aiptasia mutabilis</i>	100859	389
147	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Actiniaria	Hormathiidae	<i>Actinauge richardi</i>	100930	303
148	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Actiniaria	Hormathiidae	<i>Calliactis palliata</i>	1658483	345
149	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Actiniaria	Hormathiidae	<i>Calliactis parasitica</i>	100946	738
150	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Actiniaria	Sagartiidae	<i>Cereus pedunculatus</i>	100987	189
151	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Ceriantharia	Cerianthidae	<i>Cerianthus membranaceus</i>	101011	218
152	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Ceriantharia	Cerianthidae	<i>Cerianthus membranacea</i>	856035	169
153	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Scleractinia	Caryophylliidae	<i>Caryophyllia (Caryophyllia) inornata</i>	135141	140
154	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Scleractinia	Caryophylliidae	<i>Caryophyllia (Caryophyllia) smithii</i>	135144	141
155	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Scleractinia	Cladocoridae	<i>Cladocora caespitosa</i>	135146	598
156	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Scleractinia	Dendrophylliidae	<i>Astroides calycularis</i>	135178	131
157	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Scleractinia	Dendrophylliidae	<i>Balanophyllia (Balanophyllia) europaea</i>	135180	436
158	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Scleractinia	Dendrophylliidae	<i>Leptopsammia pruvoti</i>	135193	334
159	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Scleractinia	Oculinidae	<i>Oculina patagonica</i>	135210	130
160	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Zoantharia	Parazoanthidae	<i>Parazoanthus axinellae</i>	101055	498
161	Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	Leptothecata	Aglaopheniidae	<i>Lytocarpia myriophyllum</i>	117302	361
162	Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	Leptothecata	Plumulariidae	<i>Nemertesia antennina</i>	117809	296
163	Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	Leptothecata	Plumulariidae	<i>Nemertesia ramosa</i>	117815	248
164	Cnidaria	Octocorallia	Malacalcyonacea	Acanthogorgiidae	<i>Paramuricea clavata</i>	125387	443
165	Cnidaria	Octocorallia	Malacalcyonacea	Alcyoniidae	<i>Alcyonium acaule</i>	125331	197
166	Cnidaria	Octocorallia	Malacalcyonacea	Alcyoniidae	<i>Alcyonium coralloides</i>	125332	148

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167	Cnidaria	Octocorallia	Malacalcyonacea	Alcyoniidae	<i>Alcyonium palmatum</i>	125334	1175
168	Cnidaria	Octocorallia	Malacalcyonacea	Eunicellidae	<i>Eunicella cavolini</i>	125361	454
169	Cnidaria	Octocorallia	Malacalcyonacea	Eunicellidae	<i>Eunicella singularis</i>	125365	426
170	Cnidaria	Octocorallia	Malacalcyonacea	Eunicellidae	<i>Eunicella verrucosa</i>	125366	208
171	Cnidaria	Octocorallia	Malacalcyonacea	Gorgoniidae	<i>Leptogorgia sarmentosa</i>	125369	223
172	Cnidaria	Octocorallia	Scleralcyonacea	Coralliidae	<i>Corallium rubrum</i>	125416	479
173	Cnidaria	Octocorallia	Scleralcyonacea	Funiculinidae	<i>Funiculina quadrangularis</i>	128506	719
174	Cnidaria	Octocorallia	Scleralcyonacea	Keratoisididae	<i>Isidella elongata</i>	125373	252
175	Cnidaria	Octocorallia	Scleralcyonacea	Pennatulidae	<i>Pennatula phosphorea</i>	128517	284
176	Cnidaria	Octocorallia	Scleralcyonacea	Pennatulidae	<i>Pennatula rubra</i>	128519	505
177	Cnidaria	Octocorallia	Scleralcyonacea	Pennatulidae	<i>Pteroeides griseum</i>	181504	365
178	Cnidaria	Octocorallia	Scleralcyonacea	Veretillidae	<i>Veretillum cynomorium</i>	128536	244
179	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Forcipulatida	Asteriidae	<i>Coscinasterias tenuispina</i>	123795	344
180	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Forcipulatida	Asteriidae	<i>Marthasterias glacialis</i>	123803	733
181	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Paxillosida	Astropectinidae	<i>Astropecten aranciacus</i>	123856	702
182	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Paxillosida	Astropectinidae	<i>Astropecten bispinosus</i>	123859	344
183	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Paxillosida	Astropectinidae	<i>Astropecten irregularis</i>	123867	224
184	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Paxillosida	Astropectinidae	<i>Astropecten jonstoni</i>	123868	273
185	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Paxillosida	Astropectinidae	<i>Astropecten platyacanthus</i>	123876	122
186	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Paxillosida	Astropectinidae	<i>Astropecten spinulosus</i>	123878	218
187	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Paxillosida	Astropectinidae	<i>Tethyaster subinermis</i>	123913	529
188	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Paxillosida	Luidiidae	<i>Luidia ciliaris</i>	123920	309
189	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Paxillosida	Luidiidae	<i>Luidia sarsii</i>	123922	155
190	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Spinulosida	Echinasteridae	<i>Echinaster (Echinaster) sepositus</i>	125161	1239
191	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Valvatida	Asterinidae	<i>Anseropoda placenta</i>	123985	367
192	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Valvatida	Chaetasteridae	<i>Chaetaster longipes</i>	124004	344
193	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Valvatida	Goniasteridae	<i>Peltaster placenta</i>	124055	150
194	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Valvatida	Ophidiasteridae	<i>Hacelia attenuata</i>	124094	351

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195	Echinodermata	Asterozoa	Valvatida	Ophidiasteridae	<i>Ophidiaster ophidianus</i>	124101	279
196	Echinodermata	Crinozoa	Comatulida	Antedonidae	<i>Antedon mediterranea</i>	124208	679
197	Echinodermata	Crinozoa	Comatulida	Antedonidae	<i>Leptometra phalangium</i>	124226	268
198	Echinodermata	Echinozoa	Arbaciozoa	Arbaciidae	<i>Arbacia lixula</i>	124249	787
199	Echinodermata	Echinozoa	Camarodonta	Echinidae	<i>Echinus melo</i>	124294	627
200	Echinodermata	Echinozoa	Camarodonta	Echinidae	<i>Gracilechinus acutus</i>	532031	581
201	Echinodermata	Echinozoa	Camarodonta	Parechinidae	<i>Paracentrotus lividus</i>	124316	826
202	Echinodermata	Echinozoa	Camarodonta	Parechinidae	<i>Psammechinus microtuberculatus</i>	124318	204
203	Echinodermata	Echinozoa	Camarodonta	Toxopneustidae	<i>Sphaerechinus granularis</i>	124427	711
204	Echinodermata	Echinozoa	Cidarozoa	Cidaridae	<i>Cidaris cidaris</i>	124257	636
205	Echinodermata	Echinozoa	Cidarozoa	Cidaridae	<i>Stylocidaris affinis</i>	124268	431
206	Echinodermata	Echinozoa	Diadematozoa	Diadematidae	<i>Centrostephanus longispinus</i>	124331	328
207	Echinodermata	Echinozoa	Diadematozoa	Diadematidae	<i>Diadema setosum</i>	213372	161
208	Echinodermata	Echinozoa	Spatangozoa	Brissidae	<i>Brissopsis lyrifera</i>	124373	125
209	Echinodermata	Echinozoa	Spatangozoa	Brissidae	<i>Brissus unicolor</i>	124380	166
210	Echinodermata	Echinozoa	Spatangozoa	Loveniidae	<i>Echinocardium cordatum</i>	124392	193
211	Echinodermata	Echinozoa	Spatangozoa	Schizasteridae	<i>Ova canalifera</i>	569394	128
212	Echinodermata	Echinozoa	Spatangozoa	Spatangidae	<i>Spatangus purpureus</i>	124418	637
213	Echinodermata	Holothurozoa	Dendrochirozoa	Cucumariidae	<i>Paraleptopentacta elongata</i>	1474372	185
214	Echinodermata	Holothurozoa	Dendrochirozoa	Cucumariidae	<i>Paraleptopentacta tergestina</i>	1474379	167
215	Echinodermata	Holothurozoa	Dendrochirozoa	Cucumariidae	<i>Ocnus planci</i>	124647	358
216	Echinodermata	Holothurozoa	Holothuriida	Holothuriidae	<i>Holothuria (Roweothuria) poli</i>	124525	286
217	Echinodermata	Holothurozoa	Holothuriida	Holothuriidae	<i>Holothuria (Platyperona) sanctori</i>	124528	272
218	Echinodermata	Holothurozoa	Holothuriida	Holothuriidae	<i>Holothuria (Holothuria) tubulosa</i>	125182	645
219	Echinodermata	Holothurozoa	Holothuriida	Holothuriidae	<i>Holothuria forskali</i>	1670329	427
220	Echinodermata	Holothurozoa	Synallactida	Stichopodidae	<i>Parastichopus regalis</i>	149898	1554
221	Echinodermata	Ophiurozoa	Amphilepidida	Amphiuridae	<i>Amphiura chiajei</i>	125073	209

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222	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Amphilepidida	Amphiuridae	<i>Amphiura filiformis</i>	125080	126
223	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Amphilepidida	Ophiopsilidae	<i>Ophiopsila aranea</i>	125049	177
224	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Amphilepidida	Ophiotrichidae	<i>Ophiothrix fragilis</i>	125131	472
225	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Euryalida	Gorgonocephalidae	<i>Astrospartus mediterraneus</i>	124963	144
226	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Ophiacanthida	Ophiodermatidae	<i>Ophioderma longicaudum</i>	1420120	472
227	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Ophiurida	Ophiuridae	<i>Ophiura ophiura</i>	124929	641
228	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Adapedonta	Pharidae	<i>Ensis minor</i>	140734	170
229	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Adapedonta	Pharidae	<i>Phaxas pellucidus</i>	140737	142
230	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Arcida	Arcidae	<i>Arca noae</i>	138788	627
231	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Arcida	Arcidae	<i>Barbatia barbata</i>	138793	238
232	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Arcida	Glycymerididae	<i>Glycymeris nummaria</i>	504509	164
233	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Cardiida	Cardiidae	<i>Acanthocardia aculeata</i>	138990	226
234	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Cardiida	Cardiidae	<i>Acanthocardia echinata</i>	138992	352
235	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Cardiida	Cardiidae	<i>Acanthocardia tuberculata</i>	381057	662
236	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Cardiida	Cardiidae	<i>Cerastoderma glaucum</i>	138999	176
237	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Cardiida	Donacidae	<i>Donax semistriatus</i>	139601	143
238	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Cardiida	Donacidae	<i>Donax trunculus</i>	139602	328
239	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Cardiida	Donacidae	<i>Donax venustus</i>	139603	129
240	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Cardiida	Tellinidae	<i>Peronaea planata</i>	605934	149
241	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Limida	Limidae	<i>Lima lima</i>	140233	176
242	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Limida	Limidae	<i>Limaria hians</i>	140235	146
243	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Limida	Limidae	<i>Limaria tuberculata</i>	140236	138
244	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Lucinida	Lucinidae	<i>Loripes orbiculatus</i>	875379	148
245	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Mytilida	Mytilidae	<i>Lithophaga lithophaga</i>	140459	187
246	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Mytilida	Mytilidae	<i>Mytilus galloprovincialis</i>	140481	419
247	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Nuculida	Nuculidae	<i>Nucula sulcata</i>	140592	121
248	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Ostreida	Gryphaeidae	<i>Neopycnodonte cochlear</i>	140048	417
249	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Ostreida	Margaritidae	<i>Pinctada radiata</i>	140890	132

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250	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Ostreida	Ostreidae	<i>Magallana gigas</i>	836033	131
251	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Ostreida	Ostreidae	<i>Ostrea edulis</i>	140658	292
252	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Ostreida	Pinnidae	<i>Pinna nobilis</i>	140780	714
253	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Ostreida	Pinnidae	<i>Pinna rudis</i>	140781	228
254	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Ostreida	Pteriidae	<i>Pteria hirundo</i>	140891	425
255	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Pectinida	Anomiidae	<i>Anomia ephippium</i>	138748	333
256	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Pectinida	Pectinidae	<i>Aequipecten opercularis</i>	140687	246
257	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Pectinida	Pectinidae	<i>Mimachlamys varia</i>	236719	455
258	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Pectinida	Pectinidae	<i>Pecten jacobaeus</i>	394429	353
259	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Pectinida	Spondylidae	<i>Spondylus gaederopus</i>	141549	268
260	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Venerida	Mactridae	<i>Mactra stultorum</i>	140299	384
261	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Venerida	Mactridae	<i>Spisula subtruncata</i>	140302	273
262	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Venerida	Mesodesmatidae	<i>Donacilla cornea</i>	140350	126
263	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Venerida	Veneridae	<i>Callista chione</i>	141906	264
264	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Venerida	Veneridae	<i>Chamelea gallina</i>	141907	475
265	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Venerida	Veneridae	<i>Dosinia lupinus</i>	141912	191
266	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Venerida	Veneridae	<i>Polititapes aureus</i>	246150	139
267	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Venerida	Veneridae	<i>Ruditapes decussatus</i>	231749	148
268	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Venerida	Veneridae	<i>Venus nux</i>	141935	141
269	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Venerida	Veneridae	<i>Venus verrucosa</i>	141936	378
270	Mollusca	Gastropoda		Patellidae	<i>Patella caerulea</i>	140677	356
271	Mollusca	Gastropoda		Patellidae	<i>Patella rustica</i>	140683	218
272	Mollusca	Gastropoda		Patellidae	<i>Patella ulyssiponensis</i>	140684	154
273	Mollusca	Gastropoda		Plakobranchidae	<i>Elysia timida</i>	139684	150
274	Mollusca	Gastropoda		Plakobranchidae	<i>Thuridilla hopei</i>	139687	217
275	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Aplysiida	Aplysiidae	<i>Aplysia fasciata</i>	138755	164
276	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Aplysiida	Aplysiidae	<i>Aplysia punctata</i>	138758	144
277	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Caenogastropoda incertae sedis	Cerithiidae	<i>Bittium reticulatum</i>	139054	151

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278	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Caenogastropoda incertae sedis	Cerithiidae	<i>Cerithium vulgatum</i>	139066	530
279	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Caenogastropoda incertae sedis	Turritellidae	<i>Turritellinella tricarinata</i>	1381415	361
280	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Cephalaspidea	Scaphandridae	<i>Scaphander lignarius</i>	139488	373
281	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Lepetellida	Haliotidae	<i>Haliotis tuberculata</i>	140059	390
282	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Littorinimorpha	Aporrhaidae	<i>Aporrhais pespelecani</i>	138760	535
283	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Littorinimorpha	Aporrhaidae	<i>Aporrhais serresiana</i>	138761	131
284	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Littorinimorpha	Calyptraeidae	<i>Calyptraea chinensis</i>	138961	217
285	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Littorinimorpha	Cassidae	<i>Galeodea echinophora</i>	139023	1180
286	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Littorinimorpha	Cassidae	<i>Galeodea rugosa</i>	139024	460
287	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Littorinimorpha	Cypraeidae	<i>Luria lurida</i>	139499	186
288	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Littorinimorpha	Littorinidae	<i>Echinolittorina punctata</i>	345757	123
289	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Littorinimorpha	Littorinidae	<i>Melarhaphe neritoides</i>	140266	190
290	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Littorinimorpha	Naticidae	<i>Euspira fusca</i>	140529	167
291	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Littorinimorpha	Naticidae	<i>Naticarius stercusmuscarum</i>	720574	197
292	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Littorinimorpha	Naticidae	<i>Neverita josephinia</i>	140549	210
293	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Littorinimorpha	Ranellidae	<i>Ranella olearium</i>	141115	139
294	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Littorinimorpha	Strombidae	<i>Conomurex persicus</i>	565371	129
295	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Littorinimorpha	Tonnidae	<i>Tonna galea</i>	141687	196
296	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Littorinimorpha	Vermetidae	<i>Thylacodes arenarius</i>	709464	150
297	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Littorinimorpha	Xenophoridae	<i>Xenophora crispa</i>	743862	187
298	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Columbellidae	<i>Columbella rustica</i>	139196	385
299	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Conidae	<i>Conus ventricosus</i>	428401	317
300	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Muricidae	<i>Bolinus brandaris</i>	140389	950
301	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Muricidae	<i>Hexaplex trunculus</i>	140396	698
302	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Muricidae	<i>Ocenebra erinaceus</i>	140405	129
303	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Muricidae	<i>Stramonita haemastoma</i>	140417	416
304	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Nassariidae	<i>Tritia incrassata</i>	876825	168
305	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Nassariidae	<i>Tritia mutabilis</i>	876840	234

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306	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Pisaniidae	<i>Pisania striata</i>	138924	122
307	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Tudicidae	<i>Euthria cornea</i>	181057	151
308	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Nudibranchia	Chromodorididae	<i>Felimare picta</i>	597522	307
309	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Nudibranchia	Chromodorididae	<i>Felimare tricolor</i>	597530	194
310	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Nudibranchia	Chromodorididae	<i>Felimare orsinii</i>	597533	138
311	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Nudibranchia	Chromodorididae	<i>Felimare villafranca</i>	597536	123
312	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Nudibranchia	Discodorididae	<i>Peltodoris atromaculata</i>	509315	369
313	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Nudibranchia	Facelinidae	<i>Cratena peregrina</i>	146862	355
314	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Nudibranchia	Flabellinidae	<i>Edmundsella pedata</i>	1047602	192
315	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Nudibranchia	Flabellinidae	<i>Flabellina affinis</i>	139988	372
316	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Nudibranchia	Flabellinidae	<i>Paraflabellina ischitana</i>	1048137	145
317	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Nudibranchia	Tethydidae	<i>Tethys fimbria</i>	141643	286
318	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Pleurobranchida	Pleurobranchaeidae	<i>Pleurobranchaea meckeli</i>	140818	402
319	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Trochida	Calliostomatidae	<i>Calliostoma granulum</i>	141753	513
320	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Trochida	Trochidae	<i>Phorcus articulatus</i>	689174	172
321	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Trochida	Trochidae	<i>Phorcus turbinatus</i>	689179	723
322	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Trochida	Turbinidae	<i>Bolma rugosa</i>	141855	312
323	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Umbraculida	Umbraculidae	<i>Umbraculum umbraculum</i>	141879	223
324	Mollusca	Polyplacophora	Chitonida	Chitonidae	<i>Rhyssoplax olivacea</i>	1392276	196
325	Porifera	Calcarea	Clathrinida	Clathrinidae	<i>Clathrina clathrus</i>	132275	194
326	Porifera	Demospongiae	Agelasida	Agelasidae	<i>Agelas oroides</i>	132454	303
327	Porifera	Demospongiae	Axinellida	Axinellidae	<i>Axinella damicornis</i>	132472	358
328	Porifera	Demospongiae	Axinellida	Axinellidae	<i>Axinella polypoides</i>	132487	270
329	Porifera	Demospongiae	Axinellida	Axinellidae	<i>Axinella verrucosa</i>	132499	236
330	Porifera	Demospongiae	Bubarida	Dictyonellidae	<i>Acanthella acuta</i>	132455	168
331	Porifera	Demospongiae	Chondrillida	Chondrillidae	<i>Chondrilla nucula</i>	134110	161
332	Porifera	Demospongiae	Chondrosiida	Chondrosiidae	<i>Chondrosia reniformis</i>	134112	435
333	Porifera	Demospongiae	Clionaida	Clionaidae	<i>Cliona celata</i>	134121	211

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334	Porifera	Demospongiae	Clionaida	Clionaidae	<i>Cliona viridis</i>	134146	234
335	Porifera	Demospongiae	Clionaida	Spirastrellidae	<i>Spirastrella cunctatrix</i>	134235	157
336	Porifera	Demospongiae	Dictyoceratida	Dysideidae	<i>Dysidea fragilis</i>	132324	159
337	Porifera	Demospongiae	Dictyoceratida	Dysideidae	<i>Pleraplysilla spinifera</i>	132317	138
338	Porifera	Demospongiae	Dictyoceratida	Irciniidae	<i>Ircinia oros</i>	132356	169
339	Porifera	Demospongiae	Dictyoceratida	Irciniidae	<i>Ircinia variabilis</i>	132362	238
340	Porifera	Demospongiae	Dictyoceratida	Irciniidae	<i>Sarcotragus fasciculatus</i>	165081	181
341	Porifera	Demospongiae	Dictyoceratida	Irciniidae	<i>Sarcotragus spinosulus</i>	165086	370
342	Porifera	Demospongiae	Dictyoceratida	Spongiidae	<i>Spongia (Spongia) officinalis</i>	165220	278
343	Porifera	Demospongiae	Dictyoceratida	Thorectidae	<i>Scalarispongia scalaris</i>	165376	156
344	Porifera	Demospongiae	Haplosclerida	Petrosiidae	<i>Petrosia (Petrosia) ficiformis</i>	166837	378
345	Porifera	Demospongiae	Poecilosclerida	Crambeidae	<i>Crambe crambe</i>	133445	471
346	Porifera	Demospongiae	Poecilosclerida	Hymedesmiidae	<i>Hemimycale columella</i>	133543	277
347	Porifera	Demospongiae	Poecilosclerida	Hymedesmiidae	<i>Phorbas tenacior</i>	133693	280
348	Porifera	Demospongiae	Suberitida	Suberitidae	<i>Suberites domuncula</i>	134282	550
349	Porifera	Demospongiae	Tethyida	Tethyidae	<i>Tethya aurantium</i>	134311	210
350	Porifera	Demospongiae	Tetractinellida	Theneidae	<i>Thenea muricata</i>	134106	145
351	Porifera	Demospongiae	Verongiida	Aplysinidae	<i>Aplysina aerophoba</i>	133911	444
352	Porifera	Demospongiae	Verongiida	Aplysinidae	<i>Aplysina cavernicola</i>	133913	153
353	Porifera	Homoscleromorpha	Homosclerophorida	Oscarellidae	<i>Oscarella lobularis</i>	133928	171